

ANNOTATION GUIDELINE FOR FREE-TEXT ACTIVITY FUNCTIONING INFORMATION: COMMUNICATION & COGNITION

A publication of the
Epidemiology and Biostatistics Section,
Rehabilitation Medicine Department,
National Institutes of Health Clinical Center

Version: 1.1
Date: March 2025

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	INTRODUCTION	4
1.1	USE OF THIS GUIDELINE	4
1.2	INTRODUCTION TO THE ICF AND CONCEPTUALIZATION OF FUNCTION	5
1.3	REPRESENTATION OF MENTAL FUNCTIONS IN ACTIVITIES AND PARTICIPATION	6
2	CONCEPTUALIZING COMMUNICATION & COGNITION	7
3	DATA	9
4	ANNOTATION TOOL	11
5	ANNOTATION SCHEMA	11
5.1	ENTITIES AND MENTIONS	11
5.2	ATTRIBUTES OF THE COMCOG DOMAIN	12
6	GENERAL CONSIDERATIONS FOR ANNOTATION	15
6.1	ANNOTATE FOR SEMANTICS AND NOT SYNTAX	16
6.2	GRAMMATICAL AND TYPOGRAPHICAL ERRORS	16
6.3	GENERAL GUIDELINES FOR ANNOTATING COMCOG MENTIONS	17
6.4	GENERAL GUIDELINES FOR ANNOTATING ATTRIBUTES AND VALUES	19
7	COMCOG SPECIFIC CONSIDERATIONS FOR ANNOTATION	19
7.1	COMCOG AT THE ACTIVITY VS. BODY FUNCTION LEVEL	19
7.2	MEMORY FUNCTIONS	22
8	ORGANIZATION OF ICF CONCEPTS FOR ANNOTATION	23
8.1	ICF CHAPTER D1: LEARNING AND APPLYING KNOWLEDGE	23
8.2	ICF CHAPTER D2: GENERAL TASKS AND DEMANDS	31
8.3	ICF CHAPTER D3: COMMUNICATION	39
9	TIME_BUCKET ANNOTATION EXAMPLE	44
10	SSA CONCEPTS ANNOTATION EXAMPLES	45
10.1	ADAPTATION	45
10.2	APPLIED MEMORY	45
10.3	PACING	45
10.4	PERSISTENCE	46
11	CHALLENGES AND CONSIDERATIONS FOR ANNOTATING COMCOG	46
11.1	MENTAL FUNCTION ICF B-CODES WHERE REPRESENTATION IN ICF D-CODES IS UNCLEAR	46
11.2	CONTEXT DEPENDENT ANNOTATIONS	47
11.3	ANNOTATION OF TEXT IN QUOTES	49
11.4	NEUROLOGICAL EVALUATIONS AND OTHER TESTING OF MENTAL FUNCTION	50
11.5	ANNOTATING FOR MULTIPLE DOMAINS WITHIN THE SAME PROJECT	50
11.6	HYPOTHETICAL STATEMENTS	55
12	ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	55
13	REFERENCES	56
	APPENDIX 1: ICF ACTIVITIES AND PARTICIPATION CODES FOR CHAPTERS D1-D3	58
	APPENDIX 2: REPRESENTATION OF ICF MENTAL FUNCTIONS IN ACTIVITIES AND PARTICIPATION	65
	APPENDIX 3: COMMUNICATION & COGNITION DOMAIN: SSA AND ICF CROSSWALK	67
	APPENDIX 4: SYNTHETIC NOTE ANNOTATED FOR COMMUNICATION & COGNITION	80
	APPENDIX 5: COMMON ABBREVIATIONS FOUND IN CLINICAL DOCUMENTATION OF FUNCTIONING ACTIVITY	84

TABLES

TABLE 1. ICF CODE NAMES OF THE ICF CODES/CODE RANGES VALUES	13
TABLE 2. COMCOG CONCEPTS AT THE MENTAL FUNCTION LEVEL VS. THE ACTIVITIES AND PARTICIPATION LEVEL	20
TABLE 3. EXAMPLES OF COMCOG MENTIONS OF MENTAL FUNCTIONING AT THE ACTIVITY AND PARTICIPATION LEVEL	21
TABLE 4. EXAMPLES OF TEXT NOT ANNOTATED AT THE B-CODE LEVEL	22
TABLE 5. COGNITIVE FUNCTIONING ASSISTANCE VERSUS PHYSICAL ASSISTANCE TERMS.....	36
TABLE 6. SPECIAL CONSIDERATIONS FOR COMMUNICATION	44
TABLE 7. OVERLAP OF MOBILITY DOMAIN WITH COMCOG CONCEPTS.....	50
TABLE 8. OVERLAP OF SELF-CARE AND DOMESTIC LIFE DOMAINS WITH COMCOG CONCEPTS	52
TABLE 9. OVERLAP OF IPIR DOMAIN AND COMCOG CONCEPTS	53

FIGURES

FIGURE 1. DIAGRAM OF THE ICF WITH THE ACTIVITY COMPONENT HIGHLIGHTED	5
FIGURE 2. ACTIVITIES AND PARTICIPATION COMPONENT OF THE ICF FRAMEWORK WITH COMMUNICATION & COGNITION DOMAINS HIGHLIGHTED	7
FIGURE 3. FLOWCHART OF SSA DATA USED FOR COMCOG SCHEMA DEVELOPMENT AND ANNOTATION ..	11
FIGURE 4. COMMUNICATION & COGNITION ANNOTATION SCHEMA	12
FIGURE 5. COMCOG ANNOTATION EXAMPLE	15

1 INTRODUCTION

This work is a product of the Epidemiology and Biostatistics Section of the Rehabilitation Medicine Department, National Institutes of Health (NIH) Clinical Center that uses the World Health Organization's International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF) (World Health Organization, 2001) as a framework to develop analytic tools for clinical natural language processing (NLP) and to develop vocabularies of function. The interdisciplinary team is by design composed of a diverse group of scientists, including those in health informatics, mathematics, statistics, computer science, public health, and healthcare. The annotation team that created this guideline included clinical rehabilitation domain experts with backgrounds in occupational therapy, physical therapy, and primary care medicine, as well as individuals with public health and data science expertise. Disciplines consulted on guideline development outside the annotation team included Speech Language Pathology and Psychiatry.

Creation of the guideline was driven by a use case involving a collaborative agreement with the United States (U.S.) Social Security Administration (SSA) to leverage NLP approaches to improve the disability determination process. The research purpose was to develop tools to automate extraction of relevant functional information from electronic health records (EHRs) and support medical record review by adjudicators. This guideline aims to standardize Communication & Cognition information that is documented in free-text EHRs and provide a process for annotating this information.

1.1 Use of this Guideline

We recommend that users of this guideline have a good understanding of Communication & Cognition concepts and domain expertise, or access to persons with domain expertise, who can clarify concepts and their semantic representation for annotation in clinical documentation. Though the guideline was developed for manual annotation, it can also be used to develop automated annotation tools for those interested in standardizing the clinical documentation language of Communication & Cognition.

The guideline provides a review of the ICF and how functioning at the activity level is conceptualized and identified for annotation. Familiarity with the ICF and its coding scheme is essential. The ICF can be accessed through the [online ICF Browser](#), which outlines ICF categories with code names and descriptions. The ICF codes included in this guideline were the ones available as part of the ICF browser at the time the guideline was developed. Users of the guideline need to be aware that the ICF is a working document with ongoing updates potentially adding new codes or modifications to code names and descriptions. Users are advised to check the ICF online browser for the most updated classification and codes.

Appendices are provided as additional resources for users of the guideline. [Appendix 1](#) provides the ICF Activity and Participation Codes from the ICF browser for Chapters d1-d3: Learning and Applying Knowledge, General Tasks and Demands, and Communication. [Appendix 2](#) provides a tabular crosswalk of b-codes and d-codes for reference of ICF Mental Functions in Activities and Participation. [Appendix 3](#) provides a crosswalk between SSA criteria and ICF codes as they

relate to the Communication & Cognition domain. [Appendix 4](#) includes an example of a synthetic note annotated for Communication & Cognition. [Appendix 5](#) provides examples of common abbreviations seen in clinical documentation of activity and function.

Users of this guideline are expected to calculate their own inter-rater reliability (IRR) among annotators.

1.2 Introduction to the ICF and conceptualization of function

The ICF was used as a framework to conceptualize functioning and standardize annotation of functioning information at the activity level in EHRs for clinical NLP applications. The ICF was selected for its classification taxonomy of human functioning that has world-wide adoption and provides standardized language of functioning concepts with codes and operational definitions. Using the ICF to establish a common language for describing health and health-related states has potential to improve communication between users, permit comparison of data across countries and disciplines, and provide a systematic coding scheme to be used by health information systems.

Function is classified on multiple levels from body structures (e.g., cells and organs); to body functions (e.g., mental functions); to functioning at the level of activities and participation (e.g., self-care activities or work participation). An individual's functioning in a specific activity domain is understood as a complex relationship with dynamic interaction among a person's health condition, body structures and functions, and personal and environmental contextual factors (World Health Organization, 2001). Under this framework, disability is understood as activity limitations or participation restrictions resulting from impairments or environmental barriers. Figure 1 shows the ICF framework with the focus of this work at the activity level.

Figure 1. Diagram of the ICF with the Activity component highlighted

1.3 Representation of Mental Functions in Activities and Participation

Functioning at the activity level is recognized as a salient health care outcome for both the individual and for population health (Bickenbach et al., 2023). Health is usually experienced by an individual as the ability to participate in activities that one wants, needs, or is expected to do. Electronic health records are a rich source of functioning information. Clinical NLP has helped to extract data on human function for use in research to evaluate intervention outcomes and inform health care policy to benefit individual and population health (Hasan & Farri, 2019). These clinical NLP efforts, however, have focused primarily on body functions and structures for medical decision support, such as diagnosing diseases and determining interventions (Bickenbach et al., 2023; Newman-Griffis et al., 2019). Extraction of functioning information at the activity level is much less represented and is more challenging due to several factors including a lack of standardization of clinical documentation among providers and inconsistent representation across health systems (Newman-Griffis et al., 2019).

The Activities and Participation component of the ICF includes multiple chapters that cover relevant information for Communication & Cognition, which are highlighted below in Figure 2. In this guideline, Communication & Cognition (ComCog) are conceptualized together for the purposes of annotation as they have been found to factor closely together in previous work (Jette et al., 2019). Operationalization of the ComCog domain has been informed by the Communication & Cognition scale of the Work Disability Functional Assessment Battery (WD-FAB) (Porcino et al., 2018); the World Health Organization Disability Assessment Schedule (WHODAS) (Üstün et al., 2010); the applied cognition scale within the Activity Measure for Post-Acute Care (AM-PAC) (Coster et al., 2004); the ICF (World Health Organization, 2001); and the SSA Adult Listing of Impairments Section 12.00 – Mental Disorders (Social Security Administration, 2023). In particular, the operational definition of the ComCog domain has relied on the latter two sources – the ICF and Section 12.00 – Mental Disorders from SSA’s Adult Listing Impairments.

This guideline introduces annotation and coding of ComCog information at the activity level in support of clinical NLP efforts to automate information extraction in free-text EHRs. Though the chapters containing cognition-related information are separate chapters in the ICF, these concepts are combined for this guideline as they are often included together in clinical documentation. Similarly, communication is combined as communication and cognition often relate to and rely on each other in activity representation. Therefore, we operationalized the ICF Chapters d1: Learning and Applying Knowledge, d2: General Tasks and Demands, and d3: Communication into one domain and schema for annotation purposes to best represent mental functioning at the activity level. Codes primarily relating to applied cognition are found in chapters d1 and d2. Codes primarily relating to communication are found in chapter d3.

The ICF uses an alphanumeric system of coding in which the letters b, s, d, and e are used to denote Body Functions, Body Structures, Activities and Participation, and Environmental

Factors respectively. All codes in the Activities and Participation component of the ICF begin with a “d.” These letters are followed by a numeric code that begins with the chapter number (one digit), followed by the second level (two digits), and the third and fourth levels (one digit each). Each functioning domain in the Activities and Participation component can be considered a parent category to subcategories nested within broader concepts. In the Activities and Participation component, codes can be added to denote qualifying constructs of capacity (the person’s ability to execute a task) and performance (the actual doing of the task). In addition, more than one code category can be applied to a particular function. The alphanumeric codes used for annotating ComCog information are at the second category level beginning with the chapter letter (d), followed by a **3-digit code** with the first digit representing the chapter *number*, and the next 2 digits representing the *activity*. Note: Four-digit codes are provided in this guideline for reference of how these codes support specific activities within an ICF Chapter, but these codes are not included as part of the annotations themselves.

Figure 2 illustrates the focus areas of ComCog in this guideline in relationship to other domains within the Activities and Participation component of the ICF framework.

Figure 2. Activities and Participation component of the ICF framework with Communication & Cognition domains highlighted

2 CONCEPTUALIZING COMMUNICATION & COGNITION

Communication is defined as a process by which information is exchanged between individuals through a common system of symbols, signs, or behavior (Merriam-Webster.com Dictionary, 2024). Communication has both a receptive and an expressive component. The purpose of communication is to impart or receive a message or information and to provide possibilities to accomplish actions and activities jointly with others. Communication can have a directly

interactive component, such as an individual verbally conversing with a friend or a group of co-workers working on a task together. Communication can be of a solitary nature and not include other people directly at all, such as receiving messages in written format when reading a book or a recipe or writing a message such as a reminder note to oneself. Communication can also be non-verbal (such as in gestures and body posturing) and include sign language. Common everyday devices such as the phone, computers, or dictation machines are often used for the purposes of communication. For persons with speech and hearing difficulties, augmentative and alternative communication devices may be used to assist with communication. Communication is a process that relies upon a host of sensory-perception, language, cognitive, and motor processes. For example, sensory perception processes are used to hear someone's voice and to see how the other person is reacting during verbal communication between two people. Language processes involve decoding the spoken word to obtain its meaning.

Functional communication at the activity level refers to the everyday communication skills used in real-life and in natural social contexts. Functional communication in social contexts may include talking, but not necessitate talking to impart coherent messages. Functional communication in everyday situations necessitates interactions with a wide range of people including persons familiar with and well known to the individual, or others less known (Armstrong & Ferguson, 2010). Performance on decontextualized language tests is at the body function level and not a true measure of everyday functional communication (Armstrong & Ferguson, 2010).

Cognition is defined as the mental action or process of acquiring knowledge and understanding through thought, experience, and the senses (Dhakal & Bobrin, 2024). This includes all forms of knowing and awareness, such as perceiving, conceiving, remembering, reasoning, judging, imagining, and problem solving. The brain is the body structure where cognition occurs. The brain processes information about the external world, that exists outside the body of the person, through information that comes into the body as sensory input and is sent to the brain for perception and processing. The body functions of the eye bring visual information to the brain, and of the ear bring auditory information to the brain through neurological pathways. Once the brain receives sensory information, the brain processes it to make sense of the information. For example, in the activity of walking across a road, visual information about the surrounding environment of cars, pavement, signal lights, etc. is processed and interpreted for decisions to be made about when and where it is safe to cross the road. Auditory information from approaching cars, horns etc., is also processed and interpreted for decisions on when to cross safely.

Cognition is the function of making sense of information the brain receives and interpreting that information from the external world so decisions can be made to guide behavior that is adaptive to the situation or context the person is in. Cognitive processes have a hierarchical order from foundational mental functions to higher level cognitive functions (Duchek, 1991). Mental functions such as being conscious and alert are very basic, as is orientation to

oneself, time, place. Attention and the ability to focus and concentrate is a critical aspect of cognition for learning and laying down new memories. For example, one would not remember things that were said in a conversation if one were distracted and attention was being paid elsewhere at the time. Many functions in daily life that are more routine, automatic, and habitual, such as brushing one's teeth, or making the morning cup of coffee, rely on more basic cognitive processes.

Executive functions of the brain refer to higher level cognitive skills that come into play primarily during non-routine activity, and generally govern an individual's functional performance especially in novel and unstructured situations (Zoltan, 2007). Mental functions of executive skills relate to initiation, planning, organizing, problem-solving, mental flexibility, abstraction and concept formation, categorization, and decision-making. The highest of executive functions involve metacognition, that is cognitive skills involved in self-awareness, self-monitoring, self-evaluation, and self-correcting (Duchek, 1991).

Applied cognition and functional cognition have been described as the outward behavioral manifestation of one's internal mental cognitive processing. Applied Cognition is defined as "discrete functional activities whose performance depends most critically on application of cognitive skills, with limited movement requirements" (Coster et al., 2004). Functional Cognition is defined as "the ability to use and integrate thinking and performance skills to accomplish complex everyday activities" (Giles et al., 2017).

Nearly all aspects of human performance are guided by cognition. In summary, cognition is the way people process sensory input from the environment. This sensory input is processed by a series of mental functions, including deciding on how to act moment by moment in relationship with one's environment. Our work focuses on mental functioning observed at the activity level which are explicit actions or activity that results from cognitive processing outlined above.

To ensure mental functions relating to the concepts of cognition and communication were represented in the Activities and Participation component of the ICF, we constructed a cross-reference of ICF mental function [b-codes](#) to the Activities and Participation [d-codes](#) (see [Appendix 2](#)). Most mental function b-codes were found to have representation in the domain of Activity and Participation d-codes.

To further illustrate the ability to identify Communication & Cognition language for annotation purposes in the SSA use case, we mapped Communication & Cognition language and concepts from the B1, B3, B4 criteria of SSA's Adult Listings of Impairments for the Mental Disorders body system and the Mental Residual Function Capacity (MRFC) to the ICF codes within the ComCog domain. See [Appendix 3](#) for the crosswalk of SSA criteria to the ComCog domain for annotation.

3 DATA

Data used for ComCog guideline development and annotation came from two sources:

clinical notes from the National Institutes of Health (NIH) Clinical Center and health records submitted to the Social Security Administration (SSA) by applicants for work disability benefits. The population from both the NIH Clinical Center and SSA data was restricted to (working age) adults.

Health records within the NIH Clinical Center were provided by the NIH Biomedical Translational Research Information System (BTRIS), a resource available to NIH intramural researchers, that provides records as part of limited data sets. The NIH Office of Human Subjects Research Protection (OHRP) determined that research conducted with these limited data sets does not meet the definition of human subjects' research pursuant to 45 CFR 46 and OHRP guidance.

From the NIH limited datasets, we used 44 clinical records for exploratory analysis and testing of a preliminary ComCog schema to determine if consensus could be reached among annotators. Clinical note types included in exploratory analysis included Neuropsychological assessments, Occupational Therapy Behavioral Health Evaluations, Physical Therapy Initial/Discharge notes, Occupational Therapy Adult Evaluations and Speech Language Pathology progress notes.

The SSA dataset contained 2.5 million pages of medical evidence. We developed a technique to draw samples for annotation that were more likely to contain ComCog information. Domain experts created a list of ComCog-related key terms and short phrases that were then iteratively tested to define a page-level ComCog-relevance score used for weighted sampling, in combination with a measure of Optical Character Recognition (OCR) quality to exclude low quality pages. For any sampled page, one page before and after would be included if available and of sufficient optical character recognition (OCR) quality to provide additional context. Sampled document excerpts were between 1 and 3 pages long. This sampling technique was applied to create multiple samples of SSA excerpts for guideline development and interrater reliability (IRR) calculation. Types of documents included in the 660 files of SSA data for individual annotation included Medical Evidence of Record, Health Information Technology Medical Evidence of Record (HITMER), Consultative Examination reports (CE), Hospital records including Emergency Department records, inpatient and outpatient records, Physical Therapy and Occupational Therapy records, Lab Test reports, Progress Notes, and Outpatient Hospital Records. Other categories of records included were Medical Records general, miscellaneous medical records, and office treatment records. Figure 3 illustrates data distribution from SSA dataset to develop an annotated corpus for ComCog.

Figure 3. Flowchart of SSA Data used for ComCog schema development and annotation

4 ANNOTATION TOOL

Following a comprehensive review of available annotation tools in 2016-2017, the General Architecture for Text Engineering (GATE) software tool (Cunningham et al., 2011) was selected, due to its ease of use, portability, and customizable features that adequately met the needs of manual annotation and machine modelling. In addition, GATE did not require that the data be on a repository outside the NIH firewall and did not have a cost associated with open use. GATE is a general text processing framework that includes functionalities commonly found in typical NLP pipelines. While there are some disadvantages to this software, particularly in the realm of co-reference annotations, its utilities were sufficient to satisfy the annotation needs and purpose in creating this guideline. We chose to annotate ComCog mentions in GATE with yellow. You will find text examples throughout this guideline highlighted in yellow for text representing ComCog.

5 ANNOTATION SCHEMA

The annotation schema for the ComCog domain contains one entity (ComCog), which is further refined by attributes and values as defined below.

5.1 Entities and Mentions

ComCog Entity: A self-contained, well-defined description of functional status information related to communication and/or cognition. The gold standard for annotation is to annotate communication and cognition information that is applied in daily life as part of an activity or participation based on the operational definitions provided subsequently in this document.

ComCog Mention: A textual statement that represents an instance of an underlying ComCog entity. It is a contiguous span of tokens that make up a phrase, a simple sentence, or a complex sentence that demonstrates functional activity related to communication and/or cognition.

5.2 Attributes of the ComCog Domain

There are three attributes of the ComCog entity: ICF Codes/Code Ranges, Time_bucket, and SSA Concepts. These attributes are shown with their respective values in the annotation schema in Figure 4.

The annotation schema depicted in Figure 4 shows the ComCog entity in yellow, followed by the Attributes in blue boxes. The attribute values are in green boxes. Assigning values to ICF Codes/Code Ranges and time_bucket is mandatory. SSA Concepts values are optional for annotation.

Figure 4. Communication & Cognition Annotation Schema

5.2.1 ICF Codes/Code Ranges

Some of the concepts in the ComCog domain are represented as a “range” of ICF codes (e.g., d310_d329), and others are represented as individual codes (e.g. d163). Code ranges are used for ComCog concepts because certain individual codes are difficult to distinguish in text and specificity is better demonstrated by a code range. Code ranges are represented in the schema with an underscore between the code numbers, e.g., d110_d129, d130_d159, d210_d220, d310_d329, d330_d349, d350_d369. If an activity in a ComCog mention is represented by a code considered to be within a code range, then the code range is used for annotation. Annotation of a code range does not require all codes within the range to apply to the mention.

The names of each ICF code and code range included in the ComCog domain are listed in Table 1. For definitions of the ICF codes, please refer to [Appendix 1: ICF Activities and Participation Codes for chapters d1-d3](#).

Table 1. ICF Code Names of the ICF Codes/Code Ranges Values

ICF Code/Code Range	ICF Code Name
d110_d129	Purposeful sensory experiences
d130_d159	Basic learning
d160	Focusing attention
d163	Thinking
d166	Reading
d170	Writing
d172	Calculating
d175	Solving problems
d177	Making decisions
d179*	Applying Knowledge other specified
d210_d220	General tasks and demands
d230	Carrying out daily routine
d240	Handling stress and other psychological demands
d310_d329	Communicating - receiving
d330_d349	Communicating - producing
d350_d369	Conversation and use of communication devices and techniques

*d179 is specified in this guideline as managing money

Further guidance on applying the ICF Codes/Code Ranges values is outlined in section 6.4 (General Guidelines for Annotating Attributes and Values).

5.2.2 Time_bucket

The time_bucket attribute classifies the temporal value of a ComCog activity relative to the date of appointment recorded in the document. All ComCog values must be annotated with exactly one of the following time_bucket values:

- **Before Appointment (befappt):** designates an event that began and concluded before the day of the appointment.
- **Day of Appointment (dayofappt):** designates an event that takes place entirely on the day of the appointment.
- **After Appointment (aftappt):** designates an event that begins at some point after the day of the documented appointment.
- **Ongoing:** designates an event that begins before the day of the documented appointment, has not concluded by the day of the appointment, and that is expected to continue past the day of the appointment. Most ongoing events will be level of function information that has not changed by the time of the appointment.

Further guidance on applying the time_bucket values is outlined in section 6.4 (General Guidelines for Annotating Attributes and Values). Additional examples of these values are also included in section 9 (Time_bucket Annotation).

5.2.3 Social Security Administration Concepts

We have included four specific concepts in the ComCog schema for more relevant application to SSA's business process. These concepts are Adaptation, Applied Memory, Pacing, and Persistence. We provide operational definitions for these concepts below.

- **Adaptation:** responding appropriately to novel and unexpected situations, demands and changes (including environment, routine, situation, rules/time constraints and plans) while performing communication and cognition activities. Adaption is annotated in instances where an activity is modified to allow improved performance of that task or activity. Evidence of activity that demonstrates a person being able to adapt and not being able adapt to a situation outlined above is annotated. Annotation of coping or adjustment are not annotated as adaptation and these concepts are annotated as the ICF d-code 240: Handling Stress and other psychological demands.
- **Applied memory:** explicit descriptions of memory ability or inability as applied to activities, and not body functions. Text such as recall, remember, and forget related to an activity are annotated as applied memory.
- **Pacing:** the speed at which one works while sustaining an activity (e.g., slow, quick, taking rests, how often/how frequently one needs breaks to get a task completed). Annotate the ability to pace as well as the inability to pace while performing a task.
- **Persistence:** the ability to stick with a task over time (including work tasks) and sustaining an activity over a period of time for a cognitive reason. Syntactical cues of persistence in the text might be focuses, concentrates, sustains, etc. Annotate both the text of being able to persist at a task or activity and the inability to persist at a task or

activity. The concept of persistence is operationalized at the activity level as performing or not being able to perform a task with some duration. Needing redirection can also be annotated as lack of persistence at an activity or task.

See section 10 (SSA Concepts Annotation) for illustrative text examples of how the SSA Concepts are applied during annotation.

6 GENERAL CONSIDERATIONS FOR ANNOTATION

In examples throughout the guideline, **yellow highlight** is used to denote the ComCog mention. If a provided example does not include any yellow highlight, this indicates that the example does not include a ComCog mention and therefore would not be annotated. In these cases, the examples are followed by reasons not to annotate.

There are three steps to applying the ComCog schema for annotation using these guidelines:

- 1) **Identify ComCog information** (yellow highlight) and annotate it as the ComCog mention.
- 2) **Identify ICF Codes/Code Ranges values and time_bucket values.** There can be one or more ICF Codes/Code Ranges, but only one time_bucket value within a mention.
- 3) **Identify any/all SSA concept values** that apply to the ComCog entity.

Figure 5 below depicts this annotation workflow using an example ComCog mention:

Figure 5. ComCog Annotation Example

The following walks through a textual example of the ComCog Annotation Workflow.

Example: She reports she is thinking of returning to graduate school and shares the brochures with me for her intended program of study.

- 1) **ComCog Mention:** reports she is thinking
- 2) **ICF Codes/Code Ranges:** d330_d349 Communicating - producing and d163 Thinking
time_bucket Value: dayofappt (information reported during appointment)

3) SSA Concepts: N/A (In this example, there are no SSA Concepts.)

Note that more than one ICF Codes/Code Ranges value can be assigned to a ComCog mention if there are *distinct* concepts corresponding to each value within the mention. In the textual example above, she is both reporting, which is communication producing, and thinking, which is validated by sharing the brochures with the clinician. Reporting and thinking are two separate ComCog concepts that are captured within one mention.

6.1 Annotate for semantics and not syntax

At times, a ComCog mention can be confusing or ambiguous due to the syntax or phrasing of a sentence. Mentions of ComCog are always annotated for their meaning and not their syntax. It is also important to remember that only activities demonstrating ComCog concepts for the patient or subject are annotated; ComCog concepts relating to third parties (e.g., the provider, family members, etc.) are not captured.

Example 1: Mrs. Jones participated in a **discussion** about her health by asking questions about the newly prescribed meds

The text in Example 1 provides information about a back-and-forth communication between the provider and the patient and should be annotated. Evidence of the patient's involvement in the discussion is the context of "participated" and "by asking questions..."

Whereas in the following example there is no evidence of a back-and-forth communication between the patient and provider:

Example 2: "I discussed the plan of care with Mrs. Jones."

The text in Example 2 only informs us that the provider documented what the provider did without a response to indicate participation in a discussion took place on the part of the patient.

6.2 Grammatical and Typographical Errors

Grammatical and typographical errors do occur in clinical documentation. When annotating, do not edit the text. If the text can be understood as written and it contains ComCog information, then it should be annotated. We provide guidance and examples for annotating common errors.

With run-on words, only the text of interest is annotated. In the following example, only the string "chooses" is annotated.

Typographical error example: she **chooses**her courses for the first semester

Include misspelled words in the annotation without correcting or changing the original text.

Misspelling example: **unable to finish her homeorwok on time**

6.3 General Guidelines for Annotating ComCog Mentions

In the sections below, we provide guidance on how to annotate ComCog mentions to ensure consistency.

6.3.1 Text Span

The smallest span of text that represents the ComCog entity is annotated. Though contextual information is considered in deciding what to annotate, it is not included in the annotation itself. In some instances, annotation spans can be one word; in other cases, a longer text span is needed to capture the ComCog activity.

Pronouns, such as he and she, are not annotated unless they are within the mention and cannot be avoided (this is referred to as “collateral” text).

Punctuation is not captured unless it is within a mention and not at the beginning or end of a mention. Quotation marks (“”) around communication, such as verbatim quotes from a patient, are not captured as part of the mention.

Example 1: He **reports** his missed appointment occurred because he was in Michigan for the past week visiting family.

In Example 1, it is understood as the patient communicating about his whereabouts (d330) given that he missed an appointment. He is providing meaningful information to the clinician through his communication. Only the word “reports” is annotated in this case.

Example 2: He **spends his days going to formation, keeping appointments, watching television, and listening to the radio.**

In Example 2, the length of the mention is longer given the code d230: Carrying out daily routine requires evidence of managing daily routine, managing one’s own activity level. In this example we can see the cues of “spending his days” followed by the activities he is managing.

6.3.2 Overlapping ComCog Concepts

Each ComCog mention must stand on its own and is not permitted to overlap with other ComCog mentions. If ComCog concepts appear to overlap, then capture as a single ComCog mention.

6.3.3 Qualifiers

Include qualitative or quantitative qualifiers relating to a ComCog entity as part of the mention. Capturing qualifiers often provides further detail about the ComCog information that allows better demonstration of functioning at the activity level.

Example: He was **able to focus on his homework for many hours at a time.**

In this example, the quantity of time he can focus provides detail about how much focus the person has and further specifies the ability to focus. The quantifier “many hours at a time” provides information about persistence.

6.3.4 Goals

Goals are only annotated as mentions in the ComCog domain in two instances: 1) as a statement *from a patient* relating to a ComCog functional activity, or 2) if they are *goals that have been met or partially met* such that the functional activity has been demonstrated by the patient. Goals written by the clinician for the patient that are not designated as partially met or met are not annotated. Annotate only the word goal when the mention is from the patient, as the context around the annotation will support that it is coming from the patient. Commonly, goals coming from a patient indicate a *decision* on the part of the patient. In contrast, goals that are stated and written in clinical language that indicate they are coming from the provider are not annotated unless they are partially met or met. See examples below.

Example 1: My **goal** for care is to be able to plan, organize and carry out an anniversary party for my parents

In Example 1, the patient is choosing and has decided about a task they want to achieve.

Example 2: Goal: Elizabeth will **arrive at work on time for two consecutive weeks: goal met**

In Example 2, the goal was written by the provider and the patient met this goal, indicating she was able to carry out a daily routine for a set period of time and thus should be annotated. The longer span of text is captured to demonstrate the goal was met and therefore validates that the ComCog activity occurred.

Example 3: Goal: Elizabeth will follow instructions 75% of the time while making her therapy schedule out for next week.

In Example 3, the goal was written by a clinician without a documented outcome, and thus, we cannot determine if this activity was observed and therefore it would not be annotated.

6.3.5 Negation

Annotate information about inability, declining, refusing, or choosing not to do something related to ComCog functioning. Capturing negation allows understanding of a ComCog activity that a patient cannot do or chooses not to do.

Example 1: The patient **cannot organize her daybook without verbal cues**

Example 2: She **reported she could not follow directions** to make a new recipe last week

6.3.6 Question and Answer Formats

It is implied that the patient is communicating when a statement is made in a question-and-answer format. We annotate these instances when we determine there is ComCog information

within these questions and answers. In the following examples, there should be ComCog information in the answer section, although sometimes the answer is unintelligible. If there appears to be text after the question, which implies an answer, it is annotated as a ComCog mention.

Questions are annotated when answers are present.

Example 1: Have you ever forgotten your keys while away from home? Yes

Example 2: Do you understand how to proceed with the application? Yes

Example 3: Thoughts of hurting or killing yourself or others? xksolw

Do not annotate questions without text indicating an answer is present.

Example: Thoughts of hurting or killing yourself or others? () Yes () No

There is no information in this example that indicates an answer was provided in the text.

6.4 General Guidelines for Annotating Attributes and Values

There are several considerations for the attributes and values for ComCog mentions.

An annotator is expected to annotate with the individual ICF codes or code ranges that best fit the text, applying a code range where necessary. Note that it is possible to apply one or more distinct ICF codes or code ranges to an individual mention when distinct concepts of ComCog function are represented by each code. One mention can also have multiple SSA Concepts values if the different concepts are represented in the mention.

The Time_bucket attribute relates to when the event occurred. Keep in mind what the activity is. If someone is “reporting” an activity, the reporting itself generally happens on the day of the appointment and should be annotated as such. There are often textual cues providing information about when an activity occurred to inform assigning the time_bucket value.

Example: She reports she was unable to achieve any A’s while in college statistics class. The information is being communicated this to the clinician at the appointment. While it may seem like the activity is the statistics class, the ComCog activity is the “reporting”, which occurred during the visit. Thus, the ICF Codes/Code Ranges value is d330_d349 (Communicating - producing) and the time_bucket value is dayofappt. There are no SSA Concepts for this example.

7 COMCOG SPECIFIC CONSIDERATIONS FOR ANNOTATION

7.1 ComCog at the Activity vs. Body Function Level

There are specific considerations when annotating for ComCog information at the Activity level. The sections below provide guidance specific to ComCog information including: 1) identifying information specifically at the Activity, or ICF d-codes, level, 2) applying individual codes and code ranges in Chapter d1: Learning and Applying Knowledge, 3) including set up and

independence modifiers in Chapter d2: General tasks and demands, and 4) annotating relevant and meaningful communication information in Chapter d3: Communication.

To ensure mental functions relating to the concepts of cognition and communication were represented in the Activities and Participation component of the ICF, we constructed a cross-reference of ICF mental function **b**-codes to the Activities and Participation **d**-codes (see [Appendix 2](#)). Most mental function b-codes were found to have representation in the domain of Activity and Participation d-codes.

While we are specifically interested in annotation of applied or functional cognition information at the level of whole person functioning in daily life, we recognize that clinical documentation about cognition is often written at the body function level – mental functions specifically. Table 2 includes examples to illustrate how clinical documentation that relates to ComCog differs when written at the body function level vs. the activity level.

Table 2. ComCog Concepts at the Mental Function Level vs. the Activities and Participation Level

ComCog Concept	Mental Function level (Not Annotated)	Activities and Participation Level (Annotated)
Attention	[b140] Attention functions Her attention is poor	[d160] Focusing attention He was distracted and unable finish filling out his health care proxy form during the visit.
Memory	[b144] Memory functions Her delayed recall was very low	[d163] Thinking She further reported that she does initially forget to take her medicine although she remembers later in the day and does not miss doses completely.
Calculation	[b172] Calculation functions He is unable to do serial sevens backwards	[d172] Calculating She uses a calculator in order to compensate for her math difficulties
Thinking	[b160] Thought functions Has been going to the bathroom frequently – and feeling like she can't empty her bladder [b152] Emotional functions She feels sad	[d163] Thinking She feels it didn't help her.
Communication receiving	[b167] Mental functions of language	[d310_d329] Communicating – receiving

	Experiencing comprehension difficulties that are a decline from a previous level of functioning	He had problems understanding the materials and information in the treatment group
Orientation	[b114] Orientation functions She is oriented to time and place Oriented x 3	[d163] Thinking She found herself in a store and didn't know where she was She is oriented to situation and purpose Oriented x 4
Psychomotor functions	[b147] Psychomotor functions She presents with low mood and poor energy. Psychomotor retardation	[d210_d220] General Tasks and Demands His slow processing speed would make it difficult to complete the task in a reasonable amount of time.

Table 3 includes examples of ComCog annotations that represent mental functioning at the d-code level.

Table 3. Examples of ComCog Mentions of Mental Functioning at the Activity and Participation Level

ComCog Examples	ICF d-codes (Activity and Participation level)
Insight into his own problems was fair to adequate.	[d163] Thinking - pondering, speculating, or reflecting about the concept of one's problems
She realized she didn't have enough change for the parking meter	[d172] Calculating - applying mathematical principles to solve problems
Able to follow our conversation well	[d350] Conversation - "following" involves cognitive processing of understanding and being able to sustain a conversation
Reading and concentration difficulties	[d166] Reading - the activity involved in the comprehension and interpretation of written language. [d160] Focusing attention - intentionally focusing on specific stimuli, such as by filtering out distracting noises
Oriented to situation and purpose	[d163] Thinking - implies an understanding of the context one is in
Able to follow 2-3 step verbal instructions	[d310_d329] Communicating – receiving - receiving information in a verbal context [d210_d220] General Tasks and Demands - following instructions
Forgetful of taking medication	[d163] Thinking [d210_d220] General Tasks and Demands - completing tasks

Table 4 provides examples from clinical text that *would not be annotated* because the information is at the b-code, or impairment, level of function without application to activities.

Table 4. Examples of text not annotated at the b-code level

Text Examples (Not Annotated)	ICF b-codes (Body function level)
Insight is fair to adequate	[b1644] Insight - mental functions of awareness. No application to a specific activity.
Oriented x 3 Oriented to time, place, and person	[b114] Orientation functions - knowing and ascertaining one's relation to time, to place, to self, to others, to objects and to space.
Able to count backwards from 100 by serial sevens	[b172] Calculation functions - functions of addition, subtraction, and other simple mathematical calculations. No application to specific activity.
Could recall three items immediately and three items after five minutes	[b144] Memory functions - functions of short-term and long-term memory, immediate, recent, and remote memory; memory span; retrieval of memory; remembering; functions used in recalling and learning. This example has no real-life activity.
Was alert	[b110] Consciousness functions - state of awareness and alertness.
The claimant was asked "What would you do if you found a stamped and addressed envelope on the ground". She said, "I would put it in the mailbox."	[b164] Higher level cognitive functions - question and answer in the context of a standardized test assessing mental functions of judgment, decision-making, and problem solving. It is not at the activity level that is applied to a real-world situation rather is in a "testing" environment.

7.2 Memory Functions

Memory is observed in everyday communication and cognition. Working memory allows one to retain information while new information is being added and processed. This can be captured in clinical documentation referring to *initiating, sustaining, and completing* an activity, or in communication such as in conversation or discussions. ICF codes at the Activity and Participation level that require cognition and applying memory include d210 Undertaking a single task and d220 Undertaking multiple tasks. Memory can also be identified using d163 Thinking when there is explicit information that indicates thinking has occurred related to memory, e.g., "She thought she had entered her appointments into her day book but they were not there." For communication codes, memory is embedded in d350 Conversation and d355 Discussion. An example of a ComCog mention related to memory is "She further reported that she does initially forget to take her medicine although she remembers later in the day and does not miss doses completely," or "She was able to stay on topic and participated in group discussions." While memory is embedded in various ICF d-codes, we use the SSA Concepts

attribute for Applied Memory to further specify the role of memory when used in combination with the above-mentioned codes at the activity level.

8 Organization of ICF Concepts for Annotation

In the following sections, the specific ICF coding is operationalized with examples for ComCog. [Appendix 1](#) contains the ICF codes and detailed definitions used for annotation for Chapters d1-d3.

8.1 ICF Chapter d1: Learning and Applying Knowledge

Chapter d1 is about learning, applying knowledge that is learned, thinking, solving problems, and making decisions. The three categorical areas of functioning in this chapter used for annotation are: Purposeful Sensory Experiences (code range d110_d129); Basic Learning (code range d130_d159); and Applying Knowledge (codes d160, d163, d166, d170, d172, d175, d177, and d179). Descriptions and examples for annotation follow.

Codes and code ranges from Chapter d1 used in ComCog annotation:

- d110_d129: Purposeful sensory experiences
- d130_d159: Basic learning
- d160: Focusing attention
- d163: Thinking
- d166: Reading
- d170: Writing
- d172: Calculating
- d175: Solving problems
- d177: Making decisions
- d179: Applying knowledge, other specified and unspecified

Purposeful Sensory Experiences (d110-d129)

Intentionally experiencing visual and auditory stimuli involves paying attention/or not paying attention to meaningful activities going on in one's environment, such as watching TV, listening to music, or smelling the dirty diaper of one's child. We also include intentionally processing and reflecting on information. All the mentions related to the following codes will be annotated under the range d110_d129.

- **Watching (d110):** Using the sense of seeing intentionally to experience visual stimuli, such as visually tracking an object, or watching a sporting event, people, or children playing.

Example 1: Looking at staff

Example 1 implies looking intentionally at a visual stimulus, in this case a person, and paying attention to them.

Note: Keep an eye out for examples that might imply actively or intentionally avoiding stimuli such as “Poor eye contact”. We DO NOT annotate this kind of information as it can represent concepts not related to cognition (e.g., cultural practices). We also DO NOT annotate visual acuity as seen in Example 2.

Example 2: TESTING: static vs. dynamic visual acuity--patient could not read line while head shaking & unable to see which larger line that he could read because he needed to take a rest to relieve his nausea

- **Listening (d115):** Using the sense of hearing intentionally to experience auditory stimuli, such as listening to a radio, to the human voice, to music, to a lecture or to a story being told.

Example 1: Actively listening

Example 2: listen to other members before making assumptions

The examples above imply actively listening to stimuli.

- **Other purposeful sensing (d120):** Using the body's other basic senses intentionally to experience stimuli, such as touching and feeling textures, tasting sweets, or smelling flowers.

Example: Since she had Covid, she is unable to smell when her baby's diaper is dirty and needs changing

Basic Learning (d130-d159)

Adults that have missed out on learning typically done in childhood might instead do so in adulthood such as learning to read and write. Adults faced with impairments later in life, such as a spinal cord injury or blindness, often require basic learning of a new way of participation in activities by adaptation. Learning is life-long, therefore basic learning can occur when new understandings and new skills are required to meet new and changing environmental demands and situations, such as having to learn new skills for a job. All the mentions related to the following codes will be annotated under the code range d130-d159.

- **Acquiring language (d132):** Developing the competence to represent persons, objects, events, or feelings through words, symbols, phrases, and sentences. It refers to acquisition and reacquisition of one's first language. In adulthood, reacquisition of one's first language may apply in situations where a health condition impacts language functions in the brain, and one must re-learn how to access and use their first language.

Example: Patient uses telegraphic speech (i.e., “hungry, food”)

- **Acquiring an additional language (d133):** Developing the competence to represent persons, objects, events, feelings through words, symbols, phrases, and sentences, in an additional language such as a foreign language or signing.

Example: He is learning how to speak Spanish

Note: What language a person speaks is not annotated (e.g., Speaks fluent Spanish would not be annotated as ComCog).

- **Rehearsing (d135):** Repeating a sequence of events or symbols as a basic component of learning, such as counting by tens or practicing the recitation of a rhyme with gestures or chords on a musical instrument.

Example: He practiced driving the route to the new doctor's office the day before his appointment

- **Acquiring concepts (d137):** Developing competence to understand and use basic and complex concepts related to characteristics of things, persons, or events.

Example 1: In his program he learned how to distinguish between invasive and non-invasive plants

Example 2: used these setbacks as learning experiences

- **Acquiring information (d138):** Obtaining facts about persons, things, and events, such as asking why, what, where and how, asking for names.

Example 1: He asked for clarification when he could not understand the directions

Example 2: Good ability to learn new information

- **Learning to read (d140):** Developing the competence to read written material (including Braille and other symbols) with fluency and accuracy, such as recognizing characters and alphabet letters, sounding out written words with correct pronunciation, and understanding written words and phrases.

Example: She has had to learn how to read Braille

- **Learning to write (d145):** Developing the competence to produce symbols that represent sounds, words, or phrases in order to convey meaning (including Braille writing and other symbols), such as spelling effectively and using correct grammar.

Example: He was able to sign his name on the birthday card using his new adapted writing device

This example corresponds to the 4-digit ICF code d1450 – Acquiring skills to use writing implements. While we do not code at the 4-digit level, we make mention of it to show

that the 4-digit level codes can facilitate understanding of the concepts and offer expanded specificity under each code or code range.

- **Learning to calculate (d150):** Developing the competence to manipulate numbers and perform simple and complex mathematical operations, such as using mathematical signs for addition and subtraction and applying the correct mathematical operation to a problem.

Example: Needs help to add up her monthly living expenses

- **Acquiring skills (d155):** Developing basic and complex competencies in integrated sets of actions or tasks to be able to initiate and follow through with the acquisition of a skill, such as manipulating tools or toys or playing games.

Example: He had to learn how to use the splint for eating

Applying Knowledge (d160-d179)

This section of codes refers to a selected set of executive functions that rely on previous knowledge to be applied in activities. All codes listed under this section are used for annotation of applied cognition. All the mentions related to the following codes are annotated under their own individual ICF code and not a range of codes.

- **Focusing Attention (d160):** Intentionally focusing on specific stimuli, such as by filtering out distracting noises. Attention is integrally involved and crucial for many cognitive and communication functions and learning. It is the primary step in the memory process. Attention reflects an ability to narrow environmental focus as well as the ability to sustain and shift the focus. Attention can be directed to extra personal or intrapersonal space. Attention at the activity level does not include basic arousal or alertness which are mental functions and precursors for attention. Types of attention include focused, sustained, selective, alternating, and divided. Concentration is part of attention and involves the mental work while attending (Zoltan, 2007).

Example 1: Focused on obtaining her associate's degree

Example 2: Able to study for hours to prepare for her exam

Example 3: Able to remain focused during the interview

Example 4: Memory and concentration are adequate for the interview

Note: Mentions of "difficulty concentrating" alone are NOT annotated as ComCog mentions as this is referring to a body mental function without application in real life.

Example 5: Short attention span for completing her daily cleaning routine

Example 6: No limitations maintaining attention and concentration for tasks

Thinking (d163): Formulating and manipulating ideas, concepts, and images, whether goal-oriented or not, either alone or with others, such as creating fiction, proving a theorem, playing with ideas, brainstorming, meditating, pondering, speculating, or reflecting. Annotations of thinking need to be captured at the activity level, such as recalling information to play with ideas, brainstorming ideas, remembering instructions, and work-like procedures. Do not annotate when thinking is written at the body function level, such as “he was thinking irrationally” or “thinking is well organized”. Thinking or thoughts are only annotated if they are present, if they occur. DO NOT annotate if mention means thoughts are not present and not occurring. In addition, DO NOT annotate delusions or hallucinations mentions.

Example 1: Thoughts she would be better off dead

Example 2: Suicidal ideation/thoughts

Example 3: Suicidal ideation: Passive

In examples 2-3 above, playing with ideas, pondering, and reflecting by recalling information should be annotated.

Example 4: Precontemplative

This example implies formulating and manipulating ideas.

Example 5: Realizes

This example has to do with formulating ideas.

Example 6: Attributes

This example has to do with formulating ideas.

Example 7: Noticed or noted (if the meaning is as noticed) he could dress himself more easily using the adaptive equipment

Annotate “noticed” depending on the context if the information applies to the definition of the ICF code 163 (Thinking).

Example 8: Awareness

This example has to do with reflecting and could be annotated depending on the context (e.g. Awareness of responsibilities, risk, etc.). Awareness at the body function level of arousal is not annotated.

Example 9: She believes she is in her home

Synonym of thinking where “believe” is used with the same aim as the definition of this ICF code.

Example 10: She was able to recall what she had for breakfast.

Example 11: Memory is intact for recent and remote memory as evidenced by recall of what he had for breakfast and what he did for Thanksgiving 2012

Example 12: He is interested in abortive treatment for migraines and can't remember what has been tried in the past.

Example 13: In his opinion

Example 14: Perceived negative attention from peers/when perceives that another student is laughing

Example 15: Demonstrates good intent for communication

Example 16: Memory and concentration are adequate for the interview

The following are examples of ComCog terms written at the body function level that would not be annotated as “thinking”.

Example 1: Thought process/ Associations: logical

Example 2: Thought content/ Abnormal; thought: normal

Examples 1 and 2 refer to body functions (b160 Thought functions) related to the ideational component of the mind. Since there is no activity associated, these statements are not annotated.

Example 3: Orientation: Fully oriented; oriented x 3

If orientation (orientation function) does not specifically include situation and purpose, we do not annotate it. An exception to annotate for orientation is if it is referring to a situation or a purpose as this implies an awareness of insight beyond oneself.

Example 4: Attention: within normal limits

Example 5: Memory: intact recent

Example 6: Insight and judgement good

Like Example 3, the statements in Examples 4, 5, and 6 relate to memory function (b144), and since it is not applied to activity, we do not capture this mention.

Example 7: Attempted suicide

Contrary to ideation, a statement of attempting suicide is not a thought but an action, and so is not captured under ComCog. (This would be captured as part of our Self-Care & Domestic Life domain instead (NIH CC RMD Epidemiology & Biostatistics Section, 2025c).

Example 8: Motivated

Motivation is considered hypothetical and is not annotated. In the ICF it is also considered a body function (b130 Energy and drive functions).

Example 9: Positive for confusion

In this example, we do not have an activity that validates “confusion” and thus consider it to be a statement of mental function.

- **Reading (d166):** Performing activities involved in the comprehension and interpretation of written language (e.g. books, instructions or newspapers in text or Braille), for the *purpose of obtaining general knowledge or specific information*. This relates to performing the activities required to read and understand something for instructional or knowledge purposes. This differs from d325 Communicating with - receiving - written messages and is focused only on reading *comprehension* of any type of written material.

Example: Reading difficulties

- **Writing (d170):** Using or producing symbols or language to convey information, such as producing a written record of events or ideas or drafting a letter. This code relates to applying knowledge of correct grammar, syntax and correct spelling and writing conventions when writing. This overlaps, but also differs, from the communication domain code d345 that refers to getting the meaning across in what one writes.

Example: She delivered a poor report with grammatical and spelling errors

- **Calculating (d172):** Performing computations by applying mathematical principles to solve problems that are described in words and producing or displaying the results, such as computing the sum of three numbers or finding the result of dividing one number by another. Simple or complex calculation functions are annotated in how they are used in tasks in daily life, such as calculating the amount of material one would need to use for a craft project, or budgeting for groceries. Calculation functioning will not be annotated in the context of testing results or descriptions (such as in Neuropsychological formal exams: He was able to count backwards by serial sevens from 100). Note: **d179 Applying knowledge other specified** is used for money management and should be applied where money management is an explicit activity.

Example 1: Still needs help to add up her monthly living expenses

Example 2: Able to do simple addition and subtraction calculations

- **Solving problems (d175):** Finding solutions to questions or situations by identifying and analyzing issues, developing options and solutions, evaluating potential effects of solutions, and executing a chosen solution, such as in resolving a dispute between two people. A problem must exist and a method or methods to solve the problem be identified. Problem-solving is complex and involves solutions to meet a clear objective. Do not annotate the problem itself that is external to the individual, only annotate what the individual did to solve the problem. The context of what the problem is remains in the surrounding text.

Example 1: When half the shift workers called in sick due to Covid, he **put up a sign** at the restaurant door saying so and asking for patrons to be patient and **began filling in the work as a cook**.

Example 2: using two patches a day to help **manage** the cravings

- **Making decisions (d177):** Making a choice among options, implementing the choice, and evaluating the effects of the choice, such as selecting and purchasing a specific item, or deciding to undertake and undertaking one task from among several tasks that need to be done. Decision-making is a part of problem-solving and is the process where a choice is made among several alternatives that leads to a course of action. For annotation, mentions that mean decision-making include semantics of making a choice. The “what” of the choice is not annotated; only the cognitive or communication component of the decision is.

Example 1: **Wished** to leave

Example 2: The Veteran **does not wish** to execute an Advance Directive.

Example 3: She **does not want** to continue with therapy

Example 4: **Refused/declined** the procedure

Example 5: **Willing** to be contacted

Example 6: **Satisfied** with this

Example 7: **Accepting** her children's attitude toward her

Example 8: **Preferred** language: English

Example 9: **Rates**

Example 10: **Made informed decision**

Example 11: **Agrees/ Agreement**

Example 12: **Make funeral plans**

Note: As opposed to the mental health function of organization and planning (ICF code b164), we annotate planning as making decisions when the planning includes an activity as in the example above. Keep in mind that context is not annotated but informs the decision to annotate.

Example 13: **Chose/choose**

The word “chose” (and its derivative) is annotated, but not what the choice was.

Example 14: **Does not wish to have** another epidural

“Does not wish to have” shows the person made a choice among options from information received or learned.

Example 15: He **consented** to the procedure

Note: For Examples 11 and 15 and other similar examples, consider that they might need to be annotated with more than one ICF and/or SSA code. The word “consents” is

annotated with 3 ICF codes as it implies the person 1) received information (d310_d329 Communicating - receiving), used cognitive processing to understand, 2) decide, evaluate risk (d177 Making decisions), and 3) then expressed agreement, or disagreement (d330_d349 Communicating - producing). In addition, choice can imply an agreement or disagreement (negation), therefore annotate both.

Example 16: Would like a referral

Example 17: Would like to get back into counseling

Example 18: Stopped

Note: In making decisions, words such as “feels” or “feeling” are annotated depending on the context. Feeling is not captured if it relates to body functions such as mood/emotions (“she feels sad”) or sensations (“she feels that she cannot empty her bladder”). If these words are used to imply a decision, such as “she feels it didn’t help her,” then they are annotated. In addition, depending on context, feeling may also be captured under d163 - Thinking.

- **Applying knowledge, other specified and unspecified (d179):** This code is defined as an “other specified and unspecified” code within the ICF d1 domain. As part of the ComCog domain, this code is reserved to represent information about managing money and includes all instances of:
 - Using money to purchase foods and goods.
 - Saving/budgeting money.
 - Maintaining/monitoring a bank account.
 - Managing payments.
 - Ability to manage own benefit payments.
 - Ability to manage finances.
 - Paying and receiving change correctly.
 - Balancing a checkbook.

Example 1: She can shop and handle money herself

Example 2: His mother manages his finances

This example relies on surrounding context of understanding the patient cannot manage his own money.

Example 3: Can manage money

Example 4: Has the ability to handle her own benefit payment

8.2 ICF Chapter d2: General Tasks and Demands

Chapter d2 of the ICF is about general aspects of carrying out single or multiple tasks, organizing routines and handling stress. These items can be used in conjunction with more specific tasks or actions to identify the underlying features of the execution of tasks under different circumstances. Annotation in Chapter d2: General tasks and demands adds the cognitive component, or cognitive entities, in parallel with the physical components of a task.

This chapter was included in the ComCog domain to represent the mental and cognitive components required to perform tasks and meet activity demands. Operationalizing the (definitional) aspects of initiating and completing a task that require cognition: organizing time, space, and materials for a task; pacing task performance; and carrying out, completing, and sustaining a task.

Memory as applied in daily life can be found in textual information that refers to carrying out, completing, and sustaining a task. Long term memory is required to initiate and perform a task one understands and knows how to do. For example, in the task of making a sandwich one must remember the procedure or steps involved and apply this stored knowledge for successful completion.

Executive mental functions include the ability to organize, plan, abstract, self-regulate, problem-solve, and have cognitive flexibility, insight, and judgement (World Health Organization, 2001). Executive functioning at the activity level in daily life is captured within the d210-220 code range when clinical text refers to the person *preparing, initiating a task, organizing time, space, and materials for a task, pacing task performance, and carrying out, completing, and sustaining a task.*

The four areas of functioning in this chapter are: Undertaking a single task (d210); Undertaking multiple tasks (d220); Carrying out a daily routine (d230); and Handling stress and other psychological demands (d240). Please refer to [Appendix 1: ICF Activities and Participation Codes for Chapters d1-d3](#) for annotation guidelines and text examples that illustrate each concept of interest in this chapter. Appendix 1 is an especially useful reference for describing and differentiating various components of task execution such as performing tasks alone or with others and performing simple tasks or complex tasks at the 4-digit code level. While annotation is not done at the 4-digit code level, we refer to these codes in this guideline to provide information on concepts that apply under the 3-digit codes as an extension of the “parent” code.

Codes and code ranges from Chapter d2 used in ComCog annotation:

- d210_d220: Undertaking tasks
- d230: Carrying out daily routines
- d240: Handling stress and other psychological demands

Undertaking Tasks (d210-d220)

When annotating mentions about performing a task, there is not always a clear delineation of whether these mentions belong to ICF code d210 Undertaking a single task, d220 Undertaking multiple tasks, or both. This is because real-life examples show many instances of interrelation between these two codes, and a distinction cannot always be made according to the individual ICF code definitions. **Undertaking tasks is annotated as code range d210_220.**

Example 1: Ability to carry out instructions, to concentrate and to persist at tasks is markedly limited

Example 2: Following commands

Example 3: Follow single step instructions

Example 4: No limitations in understanding and following simple instructions and directions

Example 5: Demonstrated understanding

Demonstrated can be classified as a task depending on the context (if the patient is performing a task) or as communication (if the patient nods for example) and therefore it is important to be mindful of the context.

Note: The sentence "Demonstrated understanding" is very common and is captured as two separate annotations. "Demonstrated" is annotated as both d210-220 and d330-349, and "understanding" as d310-329.

Example 6: Taking medications as directed (or prescribed)

- **Undertaking a single task (d210):** Carrying out simple or complex and coordinated actions related to the mental and physical components of a single task, such as initiating a task, organizing time, space, and materials for a task, pacing task performance, and carrying out, completing, and sustaining a task.

Example 7: Finds it difficult to finish everything she starts.

Example 8: Applying for disability benefits

For Example 8, there is a cognitive task of filling out an application.

Example 9: Forgets what she should be doing

In this example, there is a task implied that she should be doing however, she has forgotten what the task is.

- **Undertaking multiple tasks (d220):** Carrying out simple or complex and coordinated actions as components of multiple, integrated, and complex tasks in sequence or simultaneously.

Example 1: She gathers all the cleaning supplies she would need and loads them into the car the night before her housekeeping job.

Two tasks are annotated together in Example 1 related to planning and carrying out an activity of preparing for her housekeeping job.

General Tasks and Demands (d230 and d240)

All the mentions related to the following codes will be annotated under their own particular ICF code and not a range of codes.

- **Carrying out daily routines (d230):** Carrying out simple or complex and coordinated actions to plan, manage and complete the requirements of day-to-day procedures or duties, such as budgeting time and making plans for separate activities throughout the day. A daily routine can refer to simple habitual activities involved in self-care and domestic life, or more complex activities that are part of one's regular schedule such as participation in a job and completing job duties, or attending regular meetings (i.e., Alcoholics Anonymous).

Example 1: Reports he eats breakfast on rising, washes up, dresses for work and leaves for the train at 8:30 daily.

Example 2: Spends his days going to formation, keeping appointments, watching television, and listening to the radio

Knowledge of the Four-digit code definitions was found to be essential in the annotation of Chapter d2: General Tasks and Demands and they are provided below as well as in Appendix 1.

The cognitive component of managing one's daily routine (**d2301**) involves mental functioning of planning and organization such as scheduling time in the day so activities can occur on time and be completed as expected.

Completing the daily routine (**d2302**) is annotated when a series of sequential activities relating to how one spends one's time throughout the day is described. The span of text for this annotation may be lengthier. However, capture the full text span to capture the sequential nature of the activities.

Managing one's own activity level (**d2303**) is the ability to budget one's available energy throughout the day so day-to-day procedures and duties can be completed. For example, taking frequent short breaks so one can tolerate sitting at a computer for an 8-hour workday, or not overscheduling after-work errands so enough energy is available to make dinner for one's children.

Adapting to changes in one's daily routine (**d2304**) represents one's cognitive flexibility in being able to quickly shift and transition from a usual pattern of activities to a new set of activities when faced with an unexpected environmental demand. For example, taking a different route home from work in the car than what one usually does, in order to adapt to a traffic jam blocking the freeway and get to the elementary school in time to pick up one's child.

- **Handling stress and other psychological demands (d240):** Carrying out simple or complex and coordinated actions to manage and control the psychological demands required to carry out tasks demanding significant responsibilities and involving stress,

distraction, or crises, such as driving a vehicle during heavy traffic or taking care of many children.

Example 1: Feels totally stressed out, and she is **looking for some help**

Note: we would also capture this statement under code d330 when referring to making needs known.

Example 2: **Able to compose herself**

Example 3: “due to his PTSD, he couldn’t tolerate being sandwiched by large trucks, so he **abandoned his car in the traffic lane** and walked home.”

Again, we do not annotate at the four-digit code but provide the definitions below to further identify included concepts for the **d240 code**.

Handling responsibilities (d2400) refers to managing the “duties” of task performance. Duties can be formal such as part of one’s job expectations and can also apply to behaviors that are expected by others or oneself to fulfill one’s role as, for example, a daughter, father, friend, and caregiver.

Handling stress (d2401) refers to one’s ability to cope with pressure, emergencies or stress associated with task performance. Stressful situations that occur in one’s physical and social environments place demands on the person to respond. These situations are often perceived by the individual as stressful events. Adaptive functioning involves responding to difficult situations in a way that leads toward achieving the best outcomes possible that are within one’s control.

Handling crisis (d2402) refers to carrying out simple or complex and coordinated actions to cope with decisive turning points in a situation or times of acute danger or difficulty. This behavior is often protective and supportive to oneself and to others, such as quickly catching a toddler that is about to fall into a swimming pool. For persons with mental impairments, stress can sometimes bring on or exacerbate psychologically based symptoms. Though we are not annotating for the “why,” information about how this impacts performance is annotated.

8.2.1 Special Considerations for ICF Chapter d2: General Tasks and Demands

General Tasks and Demands is a broad ICF chapter at the activity level that has some specific areas of relevance to ComCog including the mental functioning component, contextual characteristics of the task, mental assistance in a task, and set up of activities.

- **Cognitive Assistance for Tasks and Demands (d210_d220)**
Cognitive assistance is operationally defined as another person that provides cues, without any physical hands-on help. Information related to any cognitive assist for mental functioning a person requires in daily life activities is annotated. Cognitive assist

includes prompts (verbal or non-verbal such as gestures), supervision, reminders, etc. so an activity or task can be initiated, sustained, and completed. Most people use strategies for cognitive assistance to help themselves, most often seen to help with memory. Being aware that one needs memory support and employing strategies to help oneself remember is an example of metacognition. This includes activities such as setting reminders of appointments on calendars or on phones, writing post-it notes to oneself as a reminder, etc. Text referring to this type of information will be annotated for ComCog.

As a general guideline, do not annotate for assistance in the context of activities in daily life that implies primarily physical “hands-on” help such as “minimal,” “moderate,” “maximum assistance,” “dependent,” “contact guard,” etc.

Table 5 provides a list of clinical terms that qualify as assistance for mental and cognitive functioning and should be annotated, and a list of clinical terms that are not annotated in this domain as they imply more hands-on physical assistance.

Table 5. Cognitive functioning assistance versus physical assistance terms

Cognitive Functioning Assistance - Annotate	Physical Assistance – Do NOT annotate
Supervision	Contact guard
Prompts (verbal)	Stand-by assist
Reminders	Minimal assist
Verbal cues	Moderate assist
Heavy cues	Maximum assist
Verbal assistance	Dependent (context dependent) *
Set up (context dependent) ***	Unable
Independent	Modified independence (context dependent) **
Does on one’s own	Needs assist: too broad
Needs redirection	
Assistance with sequencing	

*dependent is often documented in clinical text around assist with transfers or mobility, however, dependence in communication and cognition is sometimes documented and is annotated as such. See example 5 below.

** see examples below where modified independent applies in ComCog domain

***Set up is annotated when the set up is needed for a cognitive reason. Do not annotate set up as a physical assist.

Assist for mental functions written solely at the body functions level is not annotated. In Examples 1 and 2 below, “cues” are for assistance of body functions. These examples of body scheme and perceptual disorders are contained within specific body function codes of b2101 Visual field functions and b180 Experience of self and time functions. Unless this type of information is linked to how it affects activities in daily life in the text, it is not annotated.

Example 1: requires verbal cues for sequencing

Example 2: Cues to attend left side of body

Example 3: Supervised/supervision

The word “supervised” demonstrates a possible need for cognitive assist. It is often related to a patient’s lack of safety awareness or general “thinking” related to an activity that requires forethought to ensure safety in task execution.

Example 4: Needs redirection <25% of time while filing her paperwork

Example 5: She is dependent on her husband for reminders to take her medications

In this example it is understood that she is requiring regular cognitive assistance in the form of reminders to take her medications.

Example 6: 75% of the time; able to follow single-step instructions

It is possible to find quantification information related to cognitive assistance, and this too should be annotated as an inclusion of the cognitive assistance. The word “redirection” implies a need for cognitive assist when performing and executing a task. Cases of redirection and negation of redirection are annotated.

Other considerations for Cognitive Assistance

Table 5 is a guideline and exceptions do exist. Terms usually applied to physical assistance can sometimes be written to mean assistance was of a cognitive nature.

Example 1: Required assistance with sequencing for donning clothes

As sequencing is the mental functioning of knowing the order of steps to follow to complete a task, this mention would be annotated as a cognitive assist and needs to capture what the assistance was for.

According to the Functional Independent Measure (FIM) (Kidd et al., 1995), Modified Independence is defined as “The patient requires an assistive device or aid, requires more than a reasonable amount of time or there is a safety risk in completing the activity.” Even though this usually means a physical aid, we can find some instances of Modified Independence for ComCog, which still means the person is independent and has good enough mental functioning to use an assistive device. As there is no physical assist in this kind of modified independence, include them as ComCog mentions.

Example 1: Medications - Modified Independence

In Example 1, modified independence might be the use of some sort of aid, such as a pill box, to support taking one’s medications at prescribed dose and times. Additionally, modified independence might also mean reminders from family members to ensure the person is taking their medications.

Example 2: The patient was modified independent in dressing (context dependent)

In Example 2, modified independence may mean the person uses an assistive device such as a button hook or dressing stick to complete the dressing task. Additionally, modified independence might also mean the person can dress themselves after assisted

with set up, for example, assistance for obtaining and laying the clothes out in the order they are donned.

Example 3: He **does his own grocery shopping and meal preparation**

In Example 3, we rely on the underlying d2202 code for “undertaking multiple tasks Independently. Cues for this annotation for tasks and demands are “does his own.”

Example 4: Reported that she **takes care of daily grooming at home without reminders**

In Example 4, we understand that she is taking care of tasks without reminders, indicating she can complete the task independently. Codes that support this annotation are d2102 undertaking a simple task and d2102 undertaking a single task independently.

Set up of activities

Set up of activities has a cognitive component of preparing space, objects, and time for an activity to be accomplished smoothly and successfully.

Set up is considered the first step for successful participation in most activities. For example, to shower and wash one’s hair, one sets up the activity by making sure there is shampoo in the shower stall, towels are nearby, and that the water temperature is adequate before stepping in, etc. The ICF code range d210-220 captures the cognitive aspect of planning required for set up as “*organizing time, space and materials*” required for smooth execution of one or more tasks.

As set up is usually part of many activities, annotations captured within the range of performing tasks will likely overlap with other ICF Activity domains such as self-care or domestic life. Keep in mind only the text of set up is annotated for ComCog.

Example 1: Upper Body Dressing: Modified independent, **set up required**

Example 2: Can feed self **from set up**

Documentation is not always clear on whether the need for set up is due to a physical or cognitive issue. Annotate all mentions of a need for set up that are either 1) of a cognitive nature, or 2) if it cannot be determined by the ambiguity of the text whether the set up was for a physical or cognitive reason. **Do not annotate if the text explicitly and clearly states set up involves purely a physical assist.** In the above examples, it is ambiguous as to whether set up refers to a physical or cognitive assist, therefore it is annotated.

A clear example of set up that is solely of a cognitive nature and therefore annotated is shown in Example 1 below.

Example 1: The patient **requires assist for her clothes to be laid out in sequential order** and then she can dress herself

This example shows how set up may be described. The person can do the physical actions of dressing herself. The cognitive or mental functioning assistance in the dressing task is for providing the order in which clothes are donned, such as underwear before outerwear. The longer text span is annotated to include the language that pertains to “set up.”

A clear example of a set up that is solely a physical assist and therefore not annotated is provided in Example 2 below. The “cutting of meat” is a physical action the person cannot do due to a physical problem of tremors.

Example 2: Pt required set up for feeding via cutting of meat due to increased tremors within RUE

Chapter d2 presents other areas of potential overlap in annotation given multiple activities require cognition and communication for execution. Please see section 11.5 (Annotating for multiple domains within the same project) for further examples for reasoning and distinguishing ComCog concepts at the activity level.

8.3 ICF Chapter d3: Communication

This chapter is about general and specific features of communicating by language, signs, and symbols, including receiving and producing messages, carrying on conversations, and using communication devices and techniques (ICF, 2001). The three categorical areas of functioning in this chapter are: Communication–receiving (d310-d329); Communication-producing (d330-d349); and Conversation and use of communication devices and techniques (d350-d369). Please follow along using Appendix 1: Chapter d3 for Annotation guidelines and text examples that illustrate each concept of interest in this chapter. Note the ICF Communication codes are all annotated in code ranges that are outlined below.

Code ranges used for this chapter:

- d310_d329 Communicating - receiving
- d330_d349 Communicating - producing
- d350_d369 Conversation and use of communication devices and techniques

Communicating - receiving (d310-d329)

Often clinical text does not specify the method by which communication was received. For example, in the mention “he understood the instructions,” it is not known how the information was received (spoken, non-verbally, signed, or written). Annotate all of these mentions under the code range of d310-329 Communicating - receiving. All mentions related to the following codes will be annotated under this ICF code range.

- **Communicating with - receiving - spoken messages (d310):** Comprehending literal and implied meanings of messages in spoken language, such as understanding that a statement asserts a fact or is an idiomatic expression. This may include not understanding a joke or statements about verbal comprehension ability.

Example 1: He **smiled when the clinician complimented him** on bringing in his medication list neatly typed up.

Example 2: **able to follow directions** and tie her shoelace with one hand

- **Communicating with - receiving - nonverbal messages (d315):** Comprehending the literal and implied meanings of messages conveyed by body gestures, such as realizing that a child is tired when she rubs her eyes; general signs and symbols, such as understanding that a warning bell means that there is a fire; and in drawings and photographs, such as understanding a cartoon drawing or picture graphs.

Example: **Picks up well on non-verbal cues**

- **Communicating with - receiving - formal sign language messages (d320):** Receiving and comprehending messages in formal sign language with literal and implied meaning.

Example: **Understands American sign language.**

- **Communicating with - receiving - written messages (d325):** Comprehending the literal and implied meanings of messages that are conveyed through written language (including Braille), such as following political events in the daily newspaper or understanding the intent of religious scripture. Whereas the code Reading (d166) relates to performing the activities to read, such as reading a manual or understanding something for instructional or knowledge purposes, code d325 is focused on the comprehension of any type of written material.

Example 1: Her **reading comprehension is average.**

Example 2: **Reading and concentration difficulties** limit her ability to understand messages in her chart.

This is an example of how her trouble with comprehension of written messages limits her ability to read and understand meanings. Despite the words “reading” and “concentration” in this example, code d325 applies as it relates to the impact on communication receiving.

Communicating - producing (d330-d349)

Often clinical text does not specify the method by which communication was relayed. For example, in the mention “Noted he had difficulty concentrating,” it is not known how the information was relayed (i.e., spoken, non-verbally, signed, or written). Annotate all of these mentions under the code range of d330_d349 Communicating - producing. Criteria for applying this range of codes include that the communication produced must be either telling a story or expressing facts. If there is documentation such as “stated yes” or “responded no,” this would not be annotated as communication producing at the Activity level.

- **Speaking (d330):** Producing words, phrases, and longer passages in spoken messages with literal and implied meaning, such as expressing a fact or telling a story in oral language. Sub-codes that are more developmental in definition and not likely to apply to an adult are (d3300) Producing meaningful sounds.

Example 1: verbalizes understanding

Note 1: The sentence "Verbalizes understanding" is very common, and it is captured in two separate annotations. "Verbalizes" is annotated as d330_d349, and "understanding" is captured as d310_d329.

Note 2: Also include instances of "verbalized" and "voiced"

Example 2: Patient said, "I am suffering from mental exhaustion".

Producing simple spoken messages (d3301): Using words to produce simple spoken messages such as single or few words or expressing a need may apply in cases where a person has difficulty responding verbally due to a health condition yet can still express needs from a ComCog standpoint.

Example: Indicating "need tied" is an example of producing a simple spoken message when a person is asking for their shoes to be tied before getting up to walk.

Producing complex messages (d3302) is relevant under this code defined as using words to produce complex spoken messages (complete sentences), such as giving an explanation or asking for directions. This implies that the person can produce spoken messages so that another person understands them. Therefore, text relating to the receiver understanding the person's spoken message is annotated. For example, "It was difficult to understand what she was trying to say" is from the perspective of the receiver but provides information about a person's ability to produce complex spoken messages.

In cases where one has learned a first language, but a health condition later in life results in disruption of language processes, reacquisition of a first language applies and not d330 speaking. If the context involves the activity of "re-learning" a first language (such as in speech therapy), this annotation will fall under code d132 (code-range d130_d159 for our purposes: basic learning): acquiring language that includes re-acquisition of one's first language.

Non-speech vocal expression (d331): Vocalizing when aware of another person in the proximal environment, such as producing sounds when the mother is close; babbling; babbling in turn-taking activities. Vocalizing in response to speech through imitating speech-sounds in a turn taking procedure.

Due to a health condition such as autism or cerebral palsy, some adults are non-verbal but can still produce vocalizations that communicate meaningful messages – such as a squeal for happiness and excitement, a growl for dislike, a scream for fear, etc.

Example: She **squealed** in delight when she heard she would be going on the field trip. In this example, we know the squealing conveys a meaningful message because of the context around it.

- **Singing (d332):** Using tones in a sequence resulting in a melody to convey messages. In annotation this may include singling a lullaby to a baby to convey a message of going to sleep or singing a military marching song to convey camaraderie.

Example: She **sings** lullabies to her baby before bed

- **Producing nonverbal messages (d335):** Using gestures and body language, signs, and symbols, producing drawings and photographs to convey messages, such as shaking one's head to indicate disagreement or drawing a picture or diagram to convey a fact or complex idea.

Example: He **kept looking away** and seemed disinterested

- **Producing messages in formal sign language (d340):** Conveying, with formal sign language, literal and implied meaning.

Example: She **signed** what the doctor had said to her mother who was deaf.

- **Writing messages (d345):** Producing the literal and implied meanings of messages that are conveyed through written language, such as writing a letter to a friend. Whereas ICF code Writing (d170) relates to applying knowledge of correct grammar, syntax and correct spelling and writing conventions when writing, code d345, refers to getting the meaning across in what one writes.

Example: She **wrote** what she needed on a post-it note.

Conversation and use of communication devices and techniques (d350-d369)

Conversation and use of communication devices is annotated as a code range including concepts of conversation (d350), discussion (d355), using communication devices and techniques as the code range level is considered the best specificity to represent this entity. Keep in mind memory is required to sustain a conversation or discussion as outlined in section 7.2.

- **Conversation (d350):** Starting, sustaining, and ending an interchange of thoughts and ideas, carried out by means of spoken, written, signed or other forms of language, with one or more people one knows or who are strangers, in formal or casual settings.

Example 1: She **rarely initiates any conversation** with her peers/group
The word conversation has clear meaning about exchange of thoughts and ideas.

Example 2: **spoke with/ talked with** her mother from my office to make funeral plans
This example indicates a conversation or discussion must have taken place (as opposed to “spoke to”) spoke with indicated something done together.

Example 3: **In contact with**

- **Discussion (d355):** Starting, sustaining, and ending an examination of a matter, with arguments for or against, or debate carried out by means of spoken, written, sign or other forms of language, with one or more people one knows or who are strangers, in formal or casual settings.

Example 1: **Discussed** her need for closeness, independence and connection

Example 2: **Discussed** her concerns related to the treatment plan provided

Note: In this case we would only need to annotate the word “discussed” because we annotate the verb alone if what comes after indicates there was a back-and-forth communication. We do not annotate this concept if the patient is not included in any way, such as a discussion between the identified provider and another provider or a between a provider and the patient's family etc.

- **Using communication devices and techniques (d360):**
Using devices, techniques, and other means for the purposes of communicating, such as calling a friend on the telephone. Inclusions: using telecommunication devices, using writing machines and communication techniques.

Example 1: She **sits on his right side** so she can hear him better
Here the patient is using the technique of positioning herself to optimize her hearing so that she can better communicate with the other person.

Example 2: **Telephone encounter**

Context for annotation is needed here that the patient himself/herself is involved in the telephone encounter and not a provider- to- provider or to another person having the telephone encounter.

Body functions relating to voice and speech are not annotated as this is about impairment of body structure or body functions that affect the *quality* of communication. Though this type of

text often provides the reason for why communication is impaired, we do not annotate for reason.

Communication information is sometimes written from the perspective of the receiver. Table 6 provides examples and reasons to annotate or to not annotate in these situations.

Table 6. Special Considerations for Communication

Text example of Communication	Reasons for Exclusion
He was asked several times to slow down his speech	This is a strategy the other person used for their understanding. We do not annotate what others say unless someone is “speaking” or interpreting on behalf of the person.
Feels that she is worse	Feels is not annotated if it is related to emotions. No activity to demonstrate.
Speech was coherent	Body Function written as quality
Text example of Communication (Annotation in yellow highlight)	Reasons for Inclusion
It is difficult to understand what she is trying to say due to her dysphasia	[d330_d349] Communicating – producing - include the perspective of the other if it gives information about communication of the person. Do not annotate “due to her dysphasia” as that is body function level.
He spoke so fast it was difficult to understand	[d330_d349] Communicating – producing - “difficult to understand” implies limitations in “imparting a message” by the person. (Note: “so fast” is a collateral b-code, b330 Fluency and rhythm of speech functions).

9 Time_bucket Annotation Example

The time_bucket values have been defined in section 5.2.2 and are relevant specifically to the date of the note being annotated. Keep in mind the date of the note annotated and any ComCog activity performed within that date is considered present and annotated as dayofappt. The actual date references such as “7/14/2021” or “yesterday” in the text are not annotated as a value but their relevance to the date of the appointment provides the semantic cues for annotation. Examples of the values in text are found below.

- **Before Appt (befappt)**

Example: He reports he spent time thinking about his education plan.

Semantic cues of the past tense “spent” and “yesterday” require the befappt value to be applied given the definition of befappt is any activity that occurred before the date of the visit on which the note was written.

- **Day of Appt (dayofappt)**

Example: She understands the directions and fills out the Global Depression scale today. Again, the semantic cues are the (present) tense and “today” for annotation of “dayofappt”.

- **After Appt (aftappt)**

Example: He plans to pick up his paycheck and deposit it in his bank account tomorrow. Semantic cues to choose the “aftappt” value for time_bucket annotation determined by the cues of “will” and “tomorrow.”

- **Ongoing (ongoing)**

Example: He followed directions on his iPhone map application to travel to Gettysburg National Park last week and plans to use the iPhone map to travel to the National Cathedral next week.

In this example, the activity of “following directions” to travel to a destination occurred before his appointment and are expected to occur after the day of the appointment as well.

10 SSA Concepts Annotation Examples

Text examples for each SSA Concepts value are provided below. Please refer to section 5.2.3 (Social Security Administration Concepts) above for specific definitions.

10.1 Adaptation

Example: She notes she began placing her clothes out each night in the correct order to wear so she could arrive at work on time.

This example provides the adaptation the person made to allow her to be successful in getting to work on time.

10.2 Applied Memory

Example: He reports he cannot find his keys on a daily basis and is always late to work.

This example is an explicit mention of limited memory applied to losing his keys.

10.3 Pacing

Example: He reports he must maintain his 15-minute rest breaks at 10 AM and 2 PM so he doesn't overtire at work.

This example shows the patient is using pacing to preserve his functioning at work to complete the daily tasks required of him.

10.4 Persistence

Example 1: He stated he focused on getting his file folders in order for hours until they were all placed in the drawer alphabetically.

This example demonstrates performing the same task over time until completion.

Example 2: Needs redirection 25% of the time

This is an example of not being able to persist at a task and requiring assistance to stay on task.

11 CHALLENGES AND CONSIDERATIONS FOR ANNOTATING COMCOG

11.1 Mental function ICF b-codes where representation in ICF d-codes is unclear

Four mental cognitive function b-codes that do not have a direct and clear representation in the d-codes of the Activities and Participation component of the ICF are d144 Memory functions, b144 Orientation functions, b147 Psychomotor functions, and b180 Experience of self and time. We addressed memory previously in section 7.2 given it is embedded in activities across ICF chapters d1-3 and identified as a significant consideration for annotation. In this section, we provide guidance on how to deal with information relating to the remaining three mental function b-codes that are not represented by any d-codes but may be expressed in clinical text at the Activity level in the ComCog domain.

11.1.1 Orientation Functions

Orientation to person, place, time, and situation is often tested in clinical evaluations of a person's cognition. However, for one to function successfully, knowing where one is, who one is, and why one is where they are is knowledge that is known, used, and often the "background" on which more complex participation in activities can occur. Cognition required to draw upon knowledge of one's orientation involves thought functions and can be captured at the Activities and Participation level with code d163 Thinking and the SSA Concept of applied_memory. Examples of ComCog mentions for orientation include "She found herself in a store and didn't know where she was" or "unaware of prior activity." Orientation at the body function level as defined by the ICF is usually referred to in clinical text as "oriented x 3" (person, place, and time). Orientation is only annotated if it is referring to a situation or a purpose as this implies an awareness and insight of the context *beyond oneself* (e.g., when "situation" is mentioned). Clinical text referring to "orientation x 4" is annotated as it is referring to the person being oriented to situation. In the example "Orientation to place: not able to identify office building," only the highlighted text is annotated as the ComCog mention as it provides more specific information of discernment and recognition of one's environment.

11.1.2 Psychomotor functions

Psychomotor functions have to do with the speed of processing information in the brain and producing a motor action in response. This can be captured in information relating to pacing. Pacing is the speed at which information is received, processed and a response through motor actions is generated. Psychomotor retardation has been recognized as one of the most fundamental features of major depressive disorder (Bennabi et al., 2013). This can be expressed

behaviorally as taking more time to understand information and work at a slower pace such as following instructions at work that is due not to a physical impairment but to a mental slowing of processing information. Working at an appropriate and consistent pace and completing tasks in a timely manner (SSA Adult Listing of Impairments Section 12.00 – Mental Disorders Paragraph B3) are the behavioral components of psychomotor functions and can be captured at the Activities and Participation level with codes d2330 Managing one’s own activity level, d210 Undertaking a single task, and d220 Undertaking multiple tasks. An example of text to annotate for psychomotor functions related to pacing in the ComCog domain is “It would be difficult for him to complete the task in a reasonable amount of time”.

11.1.3 Experience of self and time functions

The ICF code b180 classifies mental functions related to the experience of self-identity, body image, and time functions that are of a subjective nature having to do with how someone feels about themselves, rather than an action. Distortions in these mental functions could potentially impact activities and participation. For example, due to neurological brain damage, a person may no longer feel, experience or have a mental representation of the left side of the body. Losing the mental representation of a side of one’s body is demonstrated on a behavioral level as a failure to protect and incorporate the left arm in daily life activities. These deficits often present as activity limitations such as perceiving dressing is completed when only the right side of the body is dressed, while the left side has been completely ignored.

The behavioral component of these mental functions at the Activities and Participation level can be captured in clinical documentation referring to *initiating, sustaining, and completing* an activity, which is included under d210 Undertaking a single task and d220 Undertaking multiple tasks.

11.2 Context dependent annotations

Information that is annotated must refer to concepts related to communication or cognition at the **activity level**. Following is a list of terms that could be annotated as ComCog mentions depending on the context around them and the inferences made.

- **Agrees/In agreement** – This word is captured if it implies an understanding of concepts, such as agrees to a Plan of Care, agrees to participation in a group, agrees to treatment, etc., and then communicates agreement in some way. Agrees/in agreement can be annotated as d310_d329 Communicating - receiving as well as d177 Making decisions depending on the surrounding context in the documentation.
- **Awareness** – Capture if the implication is an understanding of concepts such as being aware of risks associated with certain events or behaviors. Awareness is coded as d163 Thinking in this instance. In the example “Patient aware of diagnosis/prognosis: yes” the code range d310_d329 Communicating - receiving would be applied given there is understanding of the diagnosis/prognosis. Awareness is not annotated at the body function level of awareness as a level of consciousness.

- **Consents** – Implies a person received information, used cognitive processing to understand a message, evaluated risks, made a decision, and then expresses agreement or disagreement (i.e., did not consent) Codes used for annotation are d310_d329, d177, and d330_d359. In addition, annotate instances of patient unable to give informed consent if the implication is that the patient had difficulty using cognitive processing to make a decision.
- **Expresses** – Expressing is annotated as d330_d349 Communicating - producing and captured in the context of communicating one’s thoughts or ideas directly or indirectly to others. If the word expresses relates to an emotion, it is not annotated, such as in “expresses frustration”.
- **Feels** – if the word feels is in the context of thinking, e.g., from “Pt does not feel that she needs to be on antidepressants any longer” we can assume she has thought about this and is using “feels” not as an emotion but as a summary of her thinking, coded as d163.
- **Identifies** – Identifies can represent someone finding a solution, acknowledges something from memory, and/or speaks about the information as another term for states. Based on the context of the text it can be annotated as codes d163 Thinking, d175 Solving problems, d330_d349 Communicating - producing, and applied_memory. Identifies can also be annotated as d138 Acquiring information in the sense of identifying materials that inform care, services etc.
- **Indicates** – Often represents a statement from the patient and annotated as d330_d349 Communicating - producing. “She indicates she is able to follow directions at work.” In this context we understand she is communicating to the clinician something about a task or activity she is doing, thereby stating a fact. Keep in mind the activity should be related to the indication vs. “indicates yes” which would not be annotated.
- **Intentions** – Intentions are an outcome that one hopes to achieve. For example, one’s intention to seek treatment may be to feel better, live longer, or participate in things one enjoys doing. Certain terms are captured depending on the context that informs whether a mental functioning cognitive component is used and whether the communication is more thoughtful and not automatic (such as more automatic social niceties). Do not annotate intent when it is clearly a hypothetical statement. Intentions can be coded as d163 Thinking dependent on context.
- **Made** – We capture the word “made” depending on the context if it is related to a *task*. In the text “Patient made a meal” would be annotated as d210_d220 General tasks and demands given it requires planning, executing, and completing a task. Conversely “made a fuss” would not be annotated as a task or communication as there is no quality to the communication.
- **Notes** – “patient does note that these issues in the left knee are the worst” is an example where the patient is telling a story, other instances are about the patient identifying and then communicating via “noting” something has occurred related to themselves. Code range d330_d349 can be applied in this instance.
- **Notice** – Notice/Noticed can be a report of d163 Thinking or d175 Problem solving based on the surrounding context and can be annotated for ComCog.

- **Participates** – “Participating appropriately” in activities can be annotated as code range d210_d220 General tasks and demands. Both codes include participation in individual and group activities. The word "appropriate" demonstrates mental functioning of self-regulation and decisions to act in a way considered acceptable within a certain contextual situation.
- **Reports** – Reports can come from many different voices (patient, provider, family, the chart, etc.). Annotate “reports” as d330_d349 Communicating – producing if its meaning is explicitly the first-person voice of the patient along the lines of “patient said,” and DO NOT annotate what the patient did not say or state (e.g. Patient has no significant changes to report from last visit). Keep in mind the story being told to annotate “reports” for communication producing at the activity level.
- **Reviewed** – Depending on the context, reviewed is annotated if it is clear the provider reviewed something **with the patient**, thereby meaning the patient was involved in communication receiving and coded as d310_d329 Communicating – receiving. Often clinicians document they reviewed something but do not indicate how or if the patient received or understood it. Reviewed is also not annotated if the provider reviewed with another provider, reviewed the chart etc. as this is not an activity involving the patient in communication.
- **Seeking** – seeking can be annotated as initiation of a task such as “seeking treatment” or “seeking safety materials” as d210_d220 General tasks and demands. Seeking can also be annotated as d138 Acquiring Information for asking why, what, how and asking for names, facts about things or events such in the sense of acquiring information.
- **Talk** – Talked and talked about imply communication or discussion and can be annotated as a range code for d330_d349 Communicating – producing and/or as the range code d350_d369 Conversation and use of communication devices. Keep in mind the talking should include telling of a story or fact. Do not annotate instances of “she talked to her brother” etc. as there is no story or fact in this example of “talking.”
- **Working on** – If the patient is working on a task (as opposed to working at a job as this belongs to a different ICF domain), which can be annotated as d210_d220 General tasks and demands (e.g. Working on leaving him).
- **Would like, wants** – if there is indication in the text that the patient has made a decision and is voicing it in terms of “would like” or “wants” this could be related to d177 Making decisions based on the context e.g.: “Pt would like to have back checked” which, from a telephone encounter, this message indicates she has made a decision of what she/he wants done. Alternately “would like” can be annotated as d330_349 Communicating – producing in the instance of asking for something.

11.3 Annotation of Text in quotes

When text is in first-person language, it is usually presented within quotation marks. We understand this as a direct quote from the patient. Do NOT annotate everything in quotes as ComCog mentions of communication; only annotate instances when there is relevant ComCog information being communicated.

Example 1: He reported “I was able to call the insurance company and get clarification on my coverage by myself”

This would be annotated as it provides a task the person was able to plan and carry out on his own.

Example 2: She stated “I know the difference”

This would not be annotated as there is no relevant ComCog information from the patient.

11.4 Neurological Evaluations and other testing of mental function

Documentation of standardized tests with summary reports of mental functions are particularly tricky to annotate. It is most difficult to tease out desired ComCog information to be included at an activity level from ComCog information to be excluded at the body function level. Do not annotate objective descriptions or findings that are test items in a standardized instrument or report (e.g., “Counts backwards by serial sevens: 100, 93, 86, 79;” “Auditory comprehension is average;” “good recall;” “thinking is well organized”) as they do not provide information at the activity level relating to a real-life instance of Communication or Cognition. Documentation in test reports can be captured if there is interpretation as to how the mental function tested applies to real life situations that are within the included ICF activity codes used in this guideline.

11.5 Annotating for multiple domains within the same project

It is possible that information on functioning in some ComCog mentions overlaps with information on functioning from other ICF activity chapters. In cases like these, it is important to be aware of and differentiate among the kinds of functioning information being annotated and how to annotate them. In the tables below we demonstrate how ComCog concepts can be identified within a mention and distinguished from other activity domains in ICF coding.

Codes in the mobility domain that are likely to overlap with ComCog are d460 Moving around in different locations, d465 Moving around using equipment, d470 Using transportation, and d475 Driving. These mobility codes are described at more of an activity level and would involve a cognitive component for participation. See Table 7 for examples of overlap between mobility and ComCog concepts.

Table 7. Overlap of Mobility Domain with ComCog Concepts

Mobility Text examples	ICF Mobility domain overlap and reasoning	ComCog concepts and reasoning
He drove his car to the appointment	[d475] Driving - being in control of and moving a vehicle	[d210] Undertaking a single task Driving a moving vehicle is a highly complex activity that requires high level cognitive abilities to adapt to a

		dynamic environment that is changing moment by moment as one moves through space and from one place to another.
He propels his own wheelchair in his local community	[d465] Moving around using equipment - moving the whole body from place to place using specific devices designed to facilitate moving such as moving down the street in a self-propelled wheelchair or a walker	[d210] Undertaking a single task The cognitive component in the use and handling of mobility devices implies judgement, insight and awareness and requires one to know how to use and handle devices and apply that knowledge when moving about in the home or the community.
She gets to work on her own by bus	[d470] Using Transportation - using transportation to move around as a passenger, such as using private motorized or public transportation	[d210] Undertaking a single task The cognitive component is in the using of transportation services that requires one to know how to use transportation services and apply that knowledge when moving about in the community. In this example there is planning involved in getting to the right bus stop on time, taking the correct bus, having correct materials to pay for the bus.

Any mentions of self-care or domestic life that indicate independence, information about cognitive set up, or a need for cognitive assist are annotated. Language related to applied cognition in the self-care domain is identified in the ICF definitions using words such as “choosing,” “selecting,” “being aware of,” “knowing when to ‘seek’ help,” etc. For example, a cognitive component in dressing (d5404) is *choosing appropriate clothing* which would be coded as d177 Making decisions. The cognitive component in Toileting (d530) includes *planning and choosing an appropriate place to toilet* (d210). Looking after one’s health (d570) also has cognitive components of self-regulation such as *being aware of one’s needs* (d163), *selecting (choosing) nutritious meals* (d177), *seeking assistance when needed* (d130-d159) and *following medical advice* (d210-d220). In addition to all terms listed above, ICF definition language related

to applied cognition in the domestic life domain, may include terms such as “*planning*,” “*organizing*,” “*managing*,” “*using (appliances)*,” “*taking care of/caring for (home, others)*,” “*maintaining and repairing/fixing (objects)*,” “*assisting others*,” etc. See Table 8 for examples of overlap between self-care, domestic life, and ComCog concepts.

Table 8. Overlap of Self-Care and Domestic Life domains with ComCog concepts

Self-care or Domestic Life Text Example	ICF Self-Care and Domestic Life domain overlap and reasoning	ComCog Concepts and reasoning
Denies alcohol or drug use	[d570] Looking after one’s health Refraining from substances is considered a choice of ensuring physical and mental well-being.	[d330_d349] Communication – producing Although we do not capture this as a choice or the thinking behind it, the word “denies” is annotated as part of Communication.
Well groomed	[d520] Caring for body parts - looking after parts of the body, such as skin, face, teeth, scalp, and nails	[d210_d220] General Tasks and Demands Observation by the provider of the quality, (and not the ability) of a person’s appearance is indicative of the cognitive component of knowing how to present oneself socially.
She sets her stove timer when she bakes lasagna, so she doesn’t forget to take it out of the oven	[d630] Preparing meals - planning, organizing, cooking and serving simple and complex meals	[d210_d220] General Tasks and Demands Setting reminders and alerts for oneself to accomplish a task is a metacognitive strategy.
She was supervised for bathing	[d510] Washing oneself - washing and drying one’s body and body parts	[d210_d220] General Tasks and Demands Supervision implies cognitive assist from another person without hands on help. Supervision is often utilized to ensure safety of task execution when the person does not have the cognitive or mental capacity to do this for themselves.

Independent in dressing	[d540] Dressing - putting on and taking of clothes and garments and keeping with climatic and social conditions	[d210_d220] General Tasks and Demands Independence in ADLs or IADLs is indicative of the mental and cognitive ability to self-direct the initiation, carrying out and completing the task without cognitive assist.
-------------------------	---	--

There is likely overlap in ComCog communication with communication in the domain of Interpersonal Interactions and Relationships (IPIR) when the text involves the context of interacting with others. Communication information in the ComCog domain refers to imparting and/or receiving messages through verbal, written, reading, gestures and signs and the ability to use communication devices and strategies for the purposes of communicating with others either directly (face to face) or indirectly (writing a letter). The ComCog domain includes the cognitive aspects of communication such as comprehending messages and thinking and formulating one's thoughts to be able to start, sustain, shape, and end a conversation with others. On the other hand, communication in IPIR is more concerned with the *quality* of interactions and the *quality and type* of relationships. Both are important for communication, and information in text is likely to overlap. See Table 9 for examples of overlap between IPIR and ComCog concepts.

Table 9. Overlap of IPIR Domain and ComCog Concepts

IPIR Text Example	IPIR domain overlap and reasoning	ComCog Concepts reasoning
He loves to talk about football with his father and argue about whose team is best	[d760] Family relationships - interacting with and maintaining relationship with father	[d350_d369] Conversation and use of communication devices and techniques - initiating, maintaining, shaping or terminating an argument or debate with one person
She talks on the phone with her friend	[d750] Informal social relationships - interacting with and maintaining a relationship with a friend	[d350_d369] Conversation and use of communication devices and techniques - using communication devices
During the meeting she was able to obtain a consensus for coworkers to continue	[d740] Formal relationships - interacting with and maintaining a relationship with co-workers	[d350_d369] Conversation and use of communication devices and techniques - initiating, maintaining, shaping and terminating a

to wear masks when onsite in the office		dialogue or interchange with more than one individual, such as in starting and participating in a group interchange
---	--	---

It is also possible to find mentions of independence in activities represented by multiple ICF activity chapters. We chose to include “independence” in an activity as always representing a cognitive component and thus capture it consistently in ComCog. In this case the *task or activity is captured* if there is text written about independence, but *the word “independence” does not need to be captured*. “Independence” is captured as part of the ComCog mention as a qualifier to represent the ability to plan, organize, carry out, and manage a task for safe execution. Examples of how independence is annotated to represent cognition are shown below.

Example 1: Independence in **dressing** [d210_d220] code range or d230 when there is mention of independence in the task or activity that overlaps with ComCog. In these cases of overlap, we only annotate the **task** with an ICF code of d210_d220, or d230.

Example 2: **Independence calculating** their monthly expenses [d179]
 In Example 2, “independence” is included in the ComCog mention as it is connected to a cognitive task and is not likely to overlap with other domains.

Other mentions that contain the word “independence” but are not associated with a ComCog activity are NOT annotated.

Example: Independence in socializing
 Socializing is not ComCog information, nor does it represent planning, organizing, or managing the activity and thus this mention would not be annotated.

Further examples of capturing cognitive components in ICF Chapter d2: General tasks and demands:

Example 1: She **demonstrated good ability to position her wheelchair for the bed transfer** [d210_d220]
 In this example the patient is using cognitive functioning to place the wheelchair for a safe transfer.

Example 2: He **did not remove the wheelchair foot rests before attempting the transfer.** [d210_d220]
 In this example the cognitive functioning component is the lack of ability to plan and set up the environment for safe execution thus the longer text mention is annotated.

Example 3: **Can make her own meals** [d210_d220]

This example relates to both ComCog and Self-Care and Domestic Life domains. It is annotated for ComCog at d210_d220 code range for the components of self-directed initiation and completion of an activity task.

Example 4: The claimant is able to dress, bathe, and groom himself [d230]

This example relates to both ComCog and Self Care and Domestic Life domains. The cognitive component of this activity is noted by “himself” indicating that he can plan and carry out activities required of a daily routine independently.

11.6 Hypothetical Statements

Do not annotate hypothetical statements as ComCog mentions. Only annotate ComCog related to the patient’s activities that are observed. Syntactical cues for hypothetical statements include “will,” “could,” “may,” etc. Annotation of communication and cognition at the activity level should be done only as observed behaviors of mental functioning and not aspirational or hypothetical statements.

Examples of hypothetical statements that would not be annotated:

Example 1: She will think about the route to take tomorrow

Example 2: He reports he may speak to his professor when he has office hours next week.

The exception for annotating hypothetical statements is in the case of “expert opinion” when a provider makes a statement related to the potential ComCog functioning of a patient.

Example: “his slow processing speed would make it difficult to complete the task in a reasonable amount of time”[d210_d220]

12 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by funding from the NIH Intramural Research Program and the U.S. Social Security Administration.

13 REFERENCES

- Armstrong, E., & Ferguson, A. (2010). Language, meaning, context, and functional communication. *Aphasiology*, 24(4), 480-496. [https://doi.org/Pii 921463867](https://doi.org/Pii%20921463867)
10.1080/02687030902775157
- Bennabi, D., Vandell, P., Papaxanthis, C., Pozzo, T., & Haffen, E. (2013). Psychomotor retardation in depression: a systematic review of diagnostic, pathophysiologic, and therapeutic implications. *Biomed Res Int*, 2013, 158746. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2013/158746>
- Bickenbach, J., Rubinelli, S., Baffone, C., & Stucki, G. (2023). The human functioning revolution: Implications for health systems and sciences. *Frontiers in Science*, 1(1118512), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsci.2023.1118512>
- Coster, W. J., Haley, S. M., Ludlow, L. H., Andres, P. L., & Ni, P. S. (2004). Development of an applied cognition scale to measure rehabilitation outcomes. *Arch Phys Med Rehabil*, 85(12), 2030-2035. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apmr.2004.05.002>
- Cunningham, H., Maynard, D., & Bontcheva, K. (2011). *Text processing with GATE*. Gateway Press.
- Dhakal, A., & Bobrin, B. D. (2024). Cognitive Deficits. In *StatPearls*. StatPearls Publishing Copyright © 2024, StatPearls Publishing LLC. <https://doi.org/https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK559052/>
- Duchek, J. (1991). Cognitive dimensions of performance. In C. H. Christiansen & C. Baum (Eds.), *Occupational therapy: Overcoming human performance deficits*. SLACK Incorporated.
- Giles, G. M., Edwards, D. F., Morrison, M. T., Baum, C., & Wolf, T. J. (2017). Screening for Functional Cognition in Postacute Care and the Improving Medicare Post-Acute Care Transformation (IMPACT) Act of 2014. *Am J Occup Ther*, 71(5), 7105090010p7105090011-7105090010p7105090016. <https://doi.org/10.5014/ajot.2017.715001>
- Hasan, S. A., & Farri, O. (2019). Clinical natural language processing with deep learning. In *Data science for health care: Methodologies and applications* (pp. 147-171). Springer.
- Jette, A. M., Ni, P., Rasch, E., Marfeo, E., McDonough, C., Brandt, D., Kazis, L., & Chan, L. (2019). The Work Disability Functional Assessment Battery (WD-FAB). *Phys Med Rehabil Clin N Am*, 30(3), 561-572. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pmr.2019.03.004>
- Kidd, D., Stewart, G., Baldry, J., Johnson, J., Rossiter, D., Petruckevitch, A., & Thompson, A. J. (1995). The Functional Independence Measure: a comparative validity and reliability study. *Disability and Rehabilitation*, 17(1), 10-14. <https://doi.org/10.3109/09638289509166622>
- Merriam-Webster.com Dictionary. (2024). "Communication.". Retrieved 23 Aug. 2024., from <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/communication>
- Newman-Griffis, D., Porcino, J., Zirikly, A., Thieu, T., Camacho Maldonado, J., Ho, P. S., Ding, M., Chan, L., & Rasch, E. (2019). Broadening horizons: the case for capturing function and the role of health informatics in its use. *BMC Public Health*, 19(1), 1288. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-019-7630-3>
- NIH CC RMD Epidemiology & Biostatistics Section. (2025a). *Annotation guideline for free-text activity functioning information: Interpersonal Interactions & Relationships (1.1)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13774683>

- NIH CC RMD Epidemiology & Biostatistics Section. (2025b). *Annotation guideline for free-text activity functioning information: Mobility (1.1)*. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11074837>
- NIH CC RMD Epidemiology & Biostatistics Section. (2025c). *Annotation guideline for free-text activity functioning information: Self-Care & Domestic Life (1.1)*. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11210182>
- Porcino, J., Marfeo, B., McDonough, C., & Chan, L. (2018). The Work Disability Functional Assessment Battery (WD-FAB): Development and validation review. *Tijdschrift voor Bedrijfs- en Verzekeringsgeneeskunde*, 26, 344-349. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12498-018-0247-0>
- Social Security Administration. (2023). *Disability evaluation under social security. 12.00 Mental disorders - Adult* <https://www.ssa.gov/disability/professionals/bluebook/12.00-MentalDisorders-Adult.htm>
- Üstün, T. B., Kostanjsek, N., Chatterji, S., Rehm, J., & World Health Organization (Eds.). (2010). *Measuring health and disability : Manual for WHO Disability Assessment Schedule (WHODAS 2.0)*. World Health Organization.
<https://doi.org/https://iris.who.int/handle/10665/43974>.
- World Health Organization. (2001). *International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health: ICF*. World Health Organization.
- Zoltan, B. (2007). *Vision, perception, and cognition: A manual for the evaluation and treatment of the adult with aquired brain injury* (Fourth ed.). Slack, Inc.

APPENDIX 1: ICF ACTIVITIES AND PARTICIPATION CODES FOR CHAPTERS d1-d3

CHAPTER d1. LEARNING AND APPLYING KNOWLEDGE

CHAPTER 1 ICF (Taken from ICF Browser)	
LEARNING AND APPLYING KNOWLEDGE	
This chapter is about learning, applying the knowledge that is learned, thinking, solving problems, and making decisions.	
Purposeful sensory experiences (d110-d129)	
d110 Watching	Using the sense of seeing intentionally to experience visual stimuli, such as visually tracking an object, watching a sporting event, people, or children playing.
d115 Listening	Using the sense of hearing intentionally to experience auditory stimuli, such as listening to a radio, to the human voice, to music, to a lecture or to a story told.
d120 Other purposeful sensing	Using the body's other basic senses intentionally to experience stimuli, such as touching and feeling textures, tasting sweets or smelling flowers.
d1200 Mouthing	Exploring objects using mouth or lips.
d1201 Touching	Exploring objects using hands, fingers or other limbs or body parts. <i>Exclusions: mouthing (d1200)</i>
d1202 Smelling	Sensing objects by bringing them to the nose or the nose to objects.
d1203 Tasting	Exploring the taste of food or liquid by biting, chewing or sucking.
Basic learning (d130-d159)	
d130 Copying	Imitating or mimicking as a basic component of learning, such as copying a facial expression, a gesture, a sound, or the letters of an alphabet.
d131 Learning through actions with objects	Learning through simple actions on a single object, two or more objects, symbolic and pretend play, such as in hitting an object, banging blocks and playing with dolls or cars. <i>Exclusions: play (d9200); carrying, moving and handling objects (d430-d449)</i>
d1310 Learning through simple actions with a single object	Simple actions with a single object or toy by manipulating, banging, moving, dropping, etc.
d1311 Learning through actions by relating objects	Simple actions relating two or more objects, toys or other materials without regard for the specific features of the objects, toys or materials.
d1312 Learning through actions by relating objects with regard to specific features	Actions relating two or more objects, toys or materials with regard to specific features, e.g. lid on box, cup on saucer.
d132 Acquiring language	Developing the competence to represent persons, objects, events, or feelings through words, symbols, phrases, and sentences. <i>Inclusions: re-acquisition of language</i> <i>Exclusions: acquiring an additional language (d133); communication (d310-d399)</i>
d1320 Acquiring single words or meaningful symbols	Learning words or meaningful symbols such as graphic or manual signs or symbols.
d1321 Combining words into phrases	Learning to combine words into phrases.
d1322 Acquiring syntax	Learning to produce appropriately constructed sentences or set of sentences.
d133 Acquiring an additional language	

Developing the competence to represent persons, objects, events, feelings through words, symbols, phrases and sentences, in an additional language such as a foreign language or signing. <i>Exclusions: acquiring language (d132); communication (d310-d399)</i>	
d135 Rehearsing Repeating a sequence of events or symbols as a basic component of learning, such as counting by tens or practicing the recitation of a rhyme with gestures or chords on a musical instrument.	
d137 Acquiring concepts Developing competence to understand and use basic and complex concepts related to characteristics of things, persons or events.	
d1370 Acquiring basic concepts	Learning to use such concepts as size, form, quantity, length, same, or opposite.
d1371 Acquiring complex concepts	Learning to use such concepts as classification, grouping, reversibility, or seriation.
d138 Acquiring information Obtaining facts about persons, things and events, such as asking why, what, where and how, asking for names. <i>Exclusions: acquiring concepts (d137); acquiring skills (d155).</i>	
d140 Learning to read Developing the competence to read written material (including Braille and other symbols) with fluency and accuracy, such as recognizing characters and alphabet letters, sounding out written words with correct pronunciation, and understanding written words and phrases.	
d1400 Acquiring skills to recognize symbols	Learning basic actions of deciphering symbols such as figures, icons, characters, alphabet letters and words.
d1401 Acquiring skills to sound out written words	Learning basic actions of sounding out characters, alphabet letters, symbols and words with correct pronunciation.
d1402 Acquiring skills to understanding written words and phrases	Learning basic actions to grasp the meaning of written words and texts.
d145 Learning to write Developing the competence to produce symbols that represent sounds, words or phrases in order to convey meaning (including Braille writing and other symbols), such as spelling effectively and using correct grammar.	
d1450 Acquiring skills to use writing implements	Learning basic actions of writing down symbols or alphabet letters, such as holding a pencil, chalk or brush, writing a character or a symbol on a piece of paper, using a braille, keyboard or peripheral device (mouse).
d1451 Acquiring skills to write symbols, characters and alphabet letters	Learning basic actions to transpose a sound (morpheme) into a symbol or a character (grapheme).
d1452 Acquiring skills to write words and phrases	Learning basic actions to transpose spoken words or ideas into written words or phrases.
d150 Learning to calculate Developing the competence to manipulate numbers and perform simple and complex mathematical operations, such as using mathematical signs for addition and subtraction and applying the correct mathematical operation to a problem.	
d1500 Acquiring basic skills of numeracy	Learning elementary skills of numeracy such as counting, ordering and grouping.
d1501 Acquiring skills to recognize numerals, arithmetic signs and symbols	Learning to recognize and use numbers.
d1502 Acquiring skills in using basic operations	Learning to recognize symbols related to and to use operations of addition, subtraction, multiplication and division.
d155 Acquiring skills Developing basic and complex competencies in integrated sets of actions or tasks so as to initiate and follow through with the acquisition of a skill, such as manipulating tools or toys or playing games. <i>Inclusions: acquiring basic and complex skills</i>	

d1550 Acquiring basic skills	Learning elementary, purposeful actions, such as learning to use simple tools, such as pencils or eating utensils.
d1551 Acquiring complex skills	Learning integrated sets of actions so as to follow rules, and to sequence and coordinate one's movements, such as learning to play games (e.g. football or chess) and to use a building tool.
Applying knowledge (d160-d179)	
d160 Focusing attention Intentionally focusing on specific stimuli, such as by filtering out distracting noises.	
d1600 Focusing attention on the person	Intentionally attending to features of other persons such as their face, touch or voice.
d1601 Focusing attention on the environment	Intentionally attending to some element of the environment, such as changes in the quality, quantity or intensity of physical or social stimuli.
d163 Thinking Formulating and manipulating ideas, concepts, and images, whether goal-oriented or not, either alone or with others, such as creating fiction, proving a theorem, playing with ideas, brainstorming, meditating, pondering, speculating, or reflecting. <i>Exclusions: solving problems (d175); making decisions (d177)</i>	
d166 Reading Performing activities involved in the comprehension and interpretation of written language (e.g. books, instructions or newspapers in text or Braille), for the purpose of obtaining general knowledge or specific information. <i>Exclusions: learning to read (d140)</i>	
d170 Writing Using or producing symbols or language to convey information, such as producing a written record of events or ideas or drafting a letter. <i>Exclusions: learning to write (d145)</i>	
d1700 Using general skills and strategies of the writing process	Applying words which convey appropriate meaning, employing conventional sentence structure.
d1701 Using grammatical conventions in writing compositions	Applying standard spelling, punctuation and proper case forms etc.
d172 Calculating Performing computations by applying mathematical principles to solve problems that are described in words and producing or displaying the results, such as computing the sum of three numbers or finding the result of dividing one number by another. <i>Exclusions: learning to calculate (d150)</i>	
d1720 Using skills and strategies to perform simple numeric calculations	Performing simple numeric operations such as counting, grouping, ordering and arithmetic calculations.
d1721 Using skills and strategies to perform complex numeric operations and calculations	Applying mathematical procedures and methods such as algebra, calculus and geometry to solve problems.
d175 Solving problems Finding solutions to questions or situations by identifying and analyzing issues, developing options and solutions, evaluating potential effects of solutions, and executing a chosen solution, such as in resolving a dispute between two people <i>Inclusions: solving simple and complex problems</i> <i>Exclusions: thinking (d163); making decisions (d177)</i>	
d1750 Solving simple problems	Finding solutions to a simple problem involving a single issue or question, by identifying and analyzing the issue, developing solutions, evaluating the potential effects of the solutions and executing a chosen solution.
d1751 Solving complex problems	Finding solutions to a complex problem involving multiple and interrelated issues, or several related problems, by identifying and analyzing the issue, developing solutions, evaluating the potential effects of the solutions and executing a chosen solution.
d177 Making decisions Making a choice among options, implementing the choice, and evaluating the effects of the choice, such as selecting and purchasing a specific item, or deciding to undertake and undertaking one task from among several tasks that need to be done. <i>Exclusions: thinking (d163); solving problems (d175)</i>	
d179 Applying Knowledge, other specified and unspecified	

CHAPTER d2. GENERAL TASKS AND DEMANDS

CHAPTER 2 ICF (Taken from ICF Browser) GENERAL TASKS AND DEMANDS	
<p>This chapter is about general aspects of carrying out single or multiple tasks, organizing routines and handling stress. These items can be used in conjunction with more specific tasks or actions to identify the underlying features of the execution of tasks under different circumstances.</p>	
<p>d210 Undertaking a single task Carrying out simple or complex and coordinated actions related to the mental and physical components of a single task, such as initiating a task, organizing time, space and materials for a task, pacing task performance, and carrying out, completing, and sustaining a task. <i>Inclusions: undertaking a simple or complex task; undertaking a single task independently or in a group</i></p>	
<p>d2100 Undertaking a simple task</p>	<p>Preparing, initiating and arranging the time and space required for a simple task, executing a simple task with a single major component, such as reading a book, writing a letter, or making one's bed.</p>
<p>d2101 Undertaking a complex task</p>	<p>Preparing, initiating and arranging the time and space for a single complex task; executing a complex task with more than one component, which may be carried out in sequence or simultaneously, such as arranging the furniture in one's home or completing an assignment for school.</p>
<p>d2102 Undertaking a single task independently</p>	<p>Preparing, initiating and arranging the time and space for a simple or complex task; managing and executing a task on one's own and without the assistance of others.</p>
<p>d2103 Undertaking a single task in a group</p>	<p>Preparing, initiating and arranging the time and space for a single task, simple or complex; managing and executing a task with people who are involved in some or all steps of the task.</p>
<p>d220 Undertaking multiple tasks Carrying out simple or complex and coordinated actions as components of multiple, integrated and complex tasks in sequence or simultaneously. <i>Inclusions: undertaking multiple tasks; completing multiple tasks; undertaking multiple tasks independently and in a group</i></p>	
<p>d2200 Carrying out multiple tasks</p>	<p>Preparing, initiating and arranging the time and space needed for several tasks, and managing and executing several tasks, together or sequentially.</p>
<p>d2201 Completing multiple tasks</p>	<p>Completing several tasks, together or sequentially.</p>
<p>d2202 Undertaking multiple tasks independently</p>	<p>Preparing, initiating and arranging the time and space for multiple tasks, and managing and executing several tasks together or sequentially, on one's own and without the assistance of others.</p>
<p>d2203 Undertaking multiple tasks in a group</p>	<p>Preparing, initiating and arranging the time and space for multiple tasks, and managing and executing several tasks together or sequentially with others who are involved in some or all steps of the multiple tasks.</p>
<p>d230 Carrying out daily routine Carrying out simple or complex and coordinated actions in order to plan, manage and complete the requirements of day-to-day procedures or duties, such as budgeting time and making plans for separate activities throughout the day. <i>Inclusions: managing and completing the daily routine; managing one's own activity level</i></p>	
<p>d2301 Managing daily routine</p>	<p>Carrying out simple or complex and coordinated actions in order to plan and manage the requirements of day-to-day procedures or duties.</p>
<p>d2302 Completing the daily routine</p>	<p>Carrying out simple or complex and coordinated actions in order to complete the requirements of usual day-to-day procedures or duties, such as getting dressed, eating breakfast, leaving for school or work and returning home at the end of the day.</p>
<p>d2303 Managing one's own activity level</p>	<p>Carrying out actions and behaviors to arrange the requirements in energy and time day-to-day procedures or duties.</p>
<p>d2304 Adapting to changes in daily routine</p>	<p>Interrupting and shifting tasks and actions in response to new requirements or making a transition from a usual pattern of activities to a new set of activities as a means of fulfilling daily tasks.</p>
<p>d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands</p>	

Carrying out simple or complex and coordinated actions to manage and control the psychological demands required to carry out tasks demanding significant responsibilities and involving stress, distraction, or crises, such as driving a vehicle during heavy traffic or taking care of many children. <i>Inclusions: handling responsibilities; handling stress and crisis</i>	
d2400 Handling responsibilities	Carrying out simple or complex and coordinated actions to manage the duties of task performance and to assess the requirements of these duties.
d2401 Handling stress	Carrying out simple or complex and coordinated actions to cope with pressure, emergencies or stress associated with task performance.
d2402 Handling crisis	Carrying out simple or complex and coordinated actions to cope with decisive turning points in a situation or times of acute danger or difficulty.

CHAPTER d3. COMMUNICATION

CHAPTER 3 ICF (Taken from ICF Browser) COMMUNICATION	
This chapter is about general and specific features of communicating by language, signs and symbols, including receiving and producing messages, carrying on conversations, and using communication devices and techniques.	
Communicating - receiving (d310-d329)	
d310 Communicating with - receiving - spoken messages Comprehending literal and implied meanings of messages in spoken language, such as understanding that a statement asserts a fact or is an idiomatic expression. <i>Inclusions: communicating with - receiving - simple spoken messages, complex spoken messages</i>	
d3100 Communicating with - receiving - simple spoken messages	Comprehending the literal meaning conveyed by simple spoken messages.
d3101 Communicating with - receiving - complex spoken messages	Comprehending the literal and implied meaning conveyed by complex spoken messages.
d315 Communicating with - receiving - nonverbal messages Comprehending the literal and implied meanings of messages conveyed by gestures, symbols and drawings, such as realizing that a child is tired when she rubs her eyes or that a warning bell means that there is a fire. <i>Inclusions: communicating with - receiving - body gestures, general signs and symbols, drawings and photographs</i>	
d3150 Communicating with - receiving - body gestures	Comprehending the meaning conveyed by facial expressions, hand movements or signs, body postures, and other forms of body language.
d3151 Communicating with - receiving - general signs and symbols	Comprehending the meaning represented by public signs and symbols, such as traffic signs, warning symbols, musical or scientific notations, and icons.
d3152 Communicating with - receiving - drawings and photographs	Comprehending the meaning represented by drawings (e.g. line drawings, graphic designs, paintings, three-dimensional representations, pictograms), graphs, charts and photographs, such as understanding that an upward line on a height chart indicates that a child is growing.
d320 Communicating with - receiving - formal sign language messages Receiving and comprehending messages in formal sign language with literal and implied meaning.	
d325 Communicating with - receiving - written messages Comprehending the literal and implied meanings of messages that are conveyed through written language (including Braille), such as following political events in the daily newspaper or understanding the intent of religious scripture.	
d329 Communicating -receiving, other specified and unspecified	
Communicating - producing (d330-d349)	
d330 Speaking Producing words, phrases and longer passages in spoken messages with literal and implied meaning, such as expressing a fact or telling a story in oral language.	
d3300 Producing meaningful sounds	Using single words to label objects, persons or actions such as ball, mommy, bye-bye.

d3301 Producing simple spoken messages	Using words to produce simple spoken messages such as single or few words or expressing a need (e.g. I want ...) or feeling (e.g., I like ...).
d3302 Producing complex spoken messages	Using words to produce complex spoken messages (complete sentences) such as giving an explanation or asking for directions.
d331 Non-speech vocal expression	
Vocalizing when aware of another person in the proximal environment, such as producing sounds when the mother is close; babbling; babbling in turn-taking activities. Vocalizing in response to speech through imitating speech-sounds in a turn taking procedure. <i>Exclusions: singing (d332)</i>	
d332 Singing	
Using tones in a sequence resulting in a melody to convey messages. <i>Inclusions: humming, chanting</i>	
d335 Producing nonverbal messages	
Using gestures, symbols and drawings to convey messages, such as shaking one's head to indicate disagreement or drawing a picture or diagram to convey a fact or complex idea. <i>Inclusions: producing body gestures, signs, symbols, drawings and photographs</i>	
d3350 Producing body language	Conveying messages by intentional movements of the body, such as facial gestures (e.g. smiling, frowning, wincing), by arm and hand movements, and by postures (e.g. embracing to indicate affection or pointing to receive attention or an object).
d3351 Producing signs and symbols	Conveying meaning by using signs and symbols (e.g. icons, Bliss board, scientific symbols) and symbolic notation systems, such as using musical notation to convey a melody.
d3352 Producing drawings and photographs	Conveying meaning by drawing, painting, sketching, and making diagrams, pictures or photographs, such as drawing a map to give someone directions to a location.
d340 Producing messages in formal sign language	
Conveying, with formal sign language, literal and implied meaning.	
d345 Writing messages	
Producing the literal and implied meanings of messages that are conveyed through written language, such as writing a letter to a friend.	
d349 Communication – producing, other specified and unspecified	
Conversation and use of communication devices and techniques (d350-d369)	
d350 Conversation	
Starting, sustaining and ending an interchange of thoughts and ideas, carried out by means of spoken, written, signed or other forms of language, with one or more people one knows or who are strangers, in formal or casual settings. <i>Inclusions: starting, sustaining and ending a conversation; conversing with one or many people</i>	
d3500 Starting a conversation	Beginning an interchange, such as initiating turn-taking activity through eye-contact or other means, that leads to communication or dialogue, such as by introducing oneself, expressing customary greetings, or by introducing a topic or asking questions.
d3501 Sustaining a conversation	Continuing and shaping a dialogue or interchange by taking turns in vocalizing, speaking or signing, by adding ideas, introducing a new topic or retrieving a topic that has been previously mentioned.
d3502 Ending a conversation	Finishing a dialogue or interchange with customary termination statements or expressions and by bringing closure to the topic under discussion.
d3503 Conversing with one person	Initiating, maintaining, shaping and terminating a dialogue or interchange with one person, such as in discussing the weather with a friend.
d3504 Conversing with many people	Initiating, maintaining, shaping and terminating a dialogue or interchange with more than one individual, such as in starting and participating in a group interchange.
d355 Discussion	
Starting, sustaining and ending an examination of a matter, with arguments for or against, or debate carried out by means of spoken, written, sign or other forms of language, with one or more people one knows or who are strangers, in formal or casual settings. <i>Inclusions: discussion with one person or many people</i>	
d3550 Discussion with one person	Initiating, maintaining, shaping or terminating an argument or debate with one person.
d3551 Discussion with many people	Initiating, maintaining, shaping or terminating an argument or debate with more than one individual.

d360 Using communication devices and techniques	
Using devices, techniques and other means for the purposes of communicating, such as calling a friend on the telephone. <i>Inclusions: using telecommunication devices, using writing machines and communication techniques</i>	
d3600 Using telecommunication devices	Using telephones, computer, and other electronic devices as means of telecommunication.
d3601 Using writing machines	Using machines for writing, such as typewriters, computers and Braille writers, as a means of communication.
d3602 Using communication techniques	Performing actions and tasks involved in techniques for communicating, such as reading lips.
d369 Communication devices and techniques, other specified and unspecified	

APPENDIX 2: REPRESENTATION OF ICF MENTAL FUNCTIONS IN ACTIVITIES AND PARTICIPATION

BODY FUNCTIONS – MENTAL FUNCTIONS	b-code	ACTIVITIES AND PARTICIPATION	d-code
Global mental functions (b110-b139)			
Consciousness functions	b110	Focusing attention	d160
Orientation functions	b114	Thinking	d163
Intellectual functions	b117	Learning and Applying Knowledge	d110-d199
		Basic learning	d130-d159
Global psychosocial functions	b122	Interpersonal Interactions and Relationships	d710-d799
Temperament and personality functions	b126	Handling stress and other psychological demands	d240
		Interpersonal Interactions and Relationships	d710-d799
Energy and drive functions	b130	Carrying out daily routine	d230
Sleep functions	b134	Looking after one's health	d570
Specific mental functions (b140-b189)			
Attention functions	b140	Focusing attention	d160
Memory functions	b144	Undertaking a single task	d210
		Undertaking multiple tasks	d220
		Conversation	d350
		Discussion	d355
Psychomotor functions	b147	Managing one's own activity level	d2330
		Undertaking a single task	d210
		Undertaking multiple tasks	d220
Emotional functions	b152	Handling stress and other psychological demands	d240
		Basic interpersonal interactions	d710
		Complex interpersonal interactions	d720
Perceptual functions	b156	Watching	d110
		Listening	d115
		Other purposeful sensing	d120
		Purposeful sensory experiences	d110-d129
Thought functions	b160	Thinking	d163
Higher-level cognitive functions			
· Abstraction	b1640	Thinking	d163
· Organization and planning	b1641	Undertaking a single task	d210
		Undertaking multiple tasks	d220
		Carrying out daily routine	d230

· Time management	b1642	Carrying out daily routine	d230
· Cognitive flexibility	b1643	Adapting to changes in daily routine	d2304
· Insight	b1644	Thinking	d163
· Judgement	b1645	Making decisions	d177
· Problem Solving	b1646	Solving problems	d175
Mental functions of language	b167	Reading	d166
		Writing	d170
		Communicating - receiving	d310-d329
		Communicating - producing	d330-d349
		Conversation and use of communication devices and techniques	d350-d369
Calculation functions	b172	Calculating	d172
Mental function of sequencing complex movements	b176	Undertaking a single task	d210
		Undertaking multiple tasks	d220
		Carrying out daily routine	d230
		Handling stress and other psychological demands	d240
Experience of self and time functions	b180	none	

APPENDIX 3: COMMUNICATION & COGNITION DOMAIN: SSA AND ICF CROSSWALK

Crosswalk of SSA B1, B3, B4 and C2 criteria, SSA Mental RFC Assessment, and related ICF b and d codes

This document correlates policy language from the SSA's disability determination for adult Mental Disorders, with ICF codes from the chapters of mental functions, and activities and participation that relates to communication and cognition. The purpose of this document is to ensure all SSA policy language for determining a mental disability is represented in ICF codes that annotators can apply to determine what information is important to capture the concepts of the Communication and Cognition for NLP work.

In this document SSA's policy language relating to the domain of communication and cognition comes from two SSA sources: (1) Selected B and C criteria of the Mental Functioning Listings, and (2) the Mental Residual Functional Capacity (Mental RFC) Assessment. The selected B-Criteria from the Listing of Mental Functioning are: B1 (Understand, remember, or apply information); B3 (Concentrate, persist, or maintain pace) and B4 (Adapt or manage oneself). The C2-Criteria are: Minimal capacity to adapt to changes in one's environment; Minimal capacity to adapt to demands that are not already part of one's daily life; and Changes or increased demands have led to exacerbation of symptoms and signs and to deterioration in functioning, i.e., unable to function outside of one's home or a more restrictive setting, without substantial psychosocial supports.

To provide context, all areas and criteria of mental functioning disability by SSA are outlined below. The bolded and highlighted areas are the specific criteria relating to Communication and Cognition information that will be addressed in the crosswalk and are the focus of this document. Please note the B2 Criteria, Interact with others and not highlighted below, is described in the annotation guideline: Interpersonal Interactions and Relationships (see References) and is not part of the Communication and Cognition areas.

The **B Criteria, in SSA Adult Mental Disorders** consists of four categories:

- B1. Understand, remember, or apply information**
- B2. Interact with others
- B3. Concentrate, persist, or maintain pace**
- B4. Adapt or manage oneself**

The C2 Criteria, shown below, was not specifically used in annotation however the criteria itself did align with the codes in the ICF Communication & Cognition chapters. ICF Environmental Factor codes (e codes) were not used as those codes are to do with the environmental barriers or facilitators to activities and participation. In our use case we are interested to know how a person **adapts** to environmental demands.

The C2 Criteria in SSA Adult Mental Disorders

- Minimal capacity to adapt to changes in one’s environment;
- Minimal capacity to adapt to demands that are not already part of one’s daily life;
- Changes or increased demands have led to exacerbation of symptoms and signs and to deterioration in functioning, i.e., unable to function outside of one’s home or a more restrictive setting, without substantial psychosocial supports

The MRFC assessment is an additional document adjudicators use to record a summary of their conclusions, derived from evidence in a claimant’s file, that ranks the level of mental activity limitations within the context of the claimant’s capacity to sustain a normal workday and workweek on an ongoing basis. Please note the mRFC Criteria-C, Social Interaction, and not highlighted below, is described in the annotation guideline: Interpersonal Interactions and Relationships (see References) and is not part of the Communication and Cognition areas.

The Mental RFC Criteria

- A. **Understanding and Memory**
- B. **Sustained concentration and Persistence**
- C. Social Interaction
- D. **Adaptation**

Appendix Table 1 lays out the criteria of each of the SSA document sources for mental functioning policy, along with the related ICF codes in the areas of communication and cognition.

Appendix Table 1. Communication & Cognition areas of interest in SSA and ICF sources

Mental Residual Functional Capacity Assessment	B Criteria, in SSA Adult Mental Disorders	C Criteria in SSA Adult Mental Disorders	ICF Components, Domains, and codes
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Understanding and Memory B. Sustained concentration and Persistence C. Social Interaction D. Adaptation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> B1. Understand, remember, or apply information B2. Interact with others B3. Concentrate, persist, or maintain pace B4. Adapt or manage oneself 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> C1. Ongoing reliance on <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • medical treatment, • mental health therapy, • psychosocial support(s), • highly structured setting(s) C2. Minimal capacity to adapt to <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • changes in one’s environment • demands that are not already part of one’s daily life. • changes or increased demands have led 	<p>ICF component: Body Function Domain: Mental Functions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Global mental functions • Specific Mental functions <p>ICF Component: Activities and Participation Domain: Learning and Applying Knowledge (Chapter 1)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic Knowledge • Applying Knowledge <p>Domain: General Tasks and Demands (Chapter 2)</p>

		to exacerbation of symptoms and signs and to deterioration in functioning i.e. unable to function outside of one's home or a more restrictive setting, without substantial psychosocial supports	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Undertaking a single task • Undertaking multiple tasks • Carrying out a daily routine • Handling stress and other psychological demands <p>Domain: Communication (Chapter 3)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication – receiving • Communication - producing
--	--	--	--

In the tables below, language from the listings of [SSA's B and C criteria](#) for adult mental disorders (in blue font) and [SSA's Mental RFC Assessment](#) (in green font) are cross-walked to ICF codes in the Activities and Participation (ICF d-codes) and Body Function (ICF b-codes) chapters. Our NLP work is interested to capture the language of functioning at the ICF level of Activities and Participation.

The four tables below are crosswalks from each of SSA's B and C-criteria of mental functioning and the related Mental RFC Assessment to ICF codes. The chapters in the ICF Activities and Participation component of interest that relate to Communication & Cognition are Learning and Applying Knowledge (Chapter 1); General Tasks and Demands (Chapter 2); and Communication (Chapter 3). Though we are most interested to annotate at the level of Activities and Participation, we do however recognize that clinical documentation of communication and cognition information is often written at the level of body functions. Therefore, both b and d-ICF codes are included in this crosswalk to help annotators decide how mentions of mental functions might be represented in activities and participation codes. Bolded codes are parent ICF 3-digit codes. The listed 4-digit ICF codes are shown to give more specificity and conceptual clarity to SSA mental functioning concepts. Bolded codes are parent ICF 3-digit codes. The listed 4-digit codes are shown to give more specificity and conceptual clarity to SSA mental functioning concepts. ICF codes from other activity domains could have some overlap and are identified here with codes in italics. For further consideration of overlap please refer to the respective separate annotation guidelines also created for the SSA use case: Self Care & Domestic Life (NIH CC RMD Epidemiology & Biostatistics Section, 2025c), Mobility (NIH CC RMD Epidemiology & Biostatistics Section, 2025b), and Interpersonal Interactions & Relationships (NIH CC RMD Epidemiology & Biostatistics Section, 2025a).

The last column in Appendix Table 2-Appendix Table 5 list the ICF codes actually used for annotation of Communication & Cognition (ComCog) functioning information. Note ICF activity code ranges, e.g. d310-329 are listed where the "range" of codes was utilized to indicate the concept covered for the specific use case.

Appendix Table 2. SSA B1- Criteria: Understand, remember, or apply information

This area of mental functioning refers to the abilities to learn, recall, and use information to perform work activities.			
12.00 Mental Disorders - Adult	ICF Codes		
SSA B1- Criteria Mental RFC- A Criteria	ICF b-codes Body Function	ICF d-codes Activities/Participation	ICF codes used for ComCog annotation
Understand information	b117 intellectual functions b156 Perceptual functions b1670 Reception of language	d140 Learning to read d163 Thinking d310 Communicating-receiving spoken messages d315 Communicating-receiving nonverbal messages d3152 Communicating with-receiving-drawings and photographs d320 Communicating-receiving formal sign language d325 Communicating-receiving written messages	d163 Thinking d310-329 Communicating receiving
Remember information	b144 Memory functions b1440 Short-term memory b1441 Long-term memory b1442 Retrieval and processing of memory b1443 Working memory	d210 Undertaking a single task d220 Undertaking multiple tasks d163 Thinking	d163 Thinking d210-220 General tasks and demands
Apply information	b144 Memory functions	d210 Undertaking a single task d220 Undertaking multiple tasks	d210-220 General tasks and demands
Abilities to learn information to perform work activities	b140 Attention functions b144 Memory functions	d155 Acquiring skills d137 Acquiring concepts d138 Acquiring information d160 Focusing attention	d130-159 Basic Learning d160 Focusing attention
Abilities recall information to perform work activities The ability to remember locations	b144 Memory functions b1440 Short-term memory b1442 Retrieval and processing of memory	d210 Undertaking a single task d220 Undertaking multiple tasks	d210-220 General tasks and demands

<p>and work-like procedures</p> <p>The ability to remember very short and simple instructions</p> <p>The ability to remember detailed instructions.</p>	<p>b1441 Long-term memory</p>		
<p>Abilities to use information to perform work activities</p>	<p>b144 Memory functions b164 Higher-level cognitive functions b177 Intellectual functions</p>	<p>d163 Thinking d210 Undertaking a single task d220 Undertaking multiple tasks d2301 Managing daily routine d2302 Completing the daily routine</p>	<p>d210-220 General tasks and demands d230 Carrying out daily routine</p>
<p>Understanding and learning terms, instructions, procedures</p> <p>The ability to understand very short and simple instructions</p> <p>The ability to understand detailed instructions.</p>	<p>b144 Memory function b1640 Abstraction b1670 Reception of language b177 Intellectual functions</p>	<p>d138 Acquiring information d166 Reading d310 Communicating with - receiving - spoken messages d3100 Communicating with - receiving - simple spoken messages d3101 Communicating with - receiving - complex spoken messages d325 Communicating with - receiving - written messages d320 Communicating with - receiving - formal sign language messages</p>	<p>d130-159 Basic learning d166 Reading d310-329 Communicating - receiving</p>
<p>Following one- or two-step oral instructions to carry out a task</p> <p>The ability to carry out very short and simple instructions.</p>	<p>b1641 Organization and planning</p>	<p>d163 Thinking d210 Undertaking a single task d310 Communicating with - receiving - spoken messages d3100 Communicating with - receiving - simple spoken messages d320 Communicating with-receiving-formal sign language messages d325 Communicating with - receiving - written messages</p>	<p>d163 Thinking d210-220 General tasks and demands d310-329 Communicating - receiving</p>

Describing work activity to someone else	b167 Mental functions of language b1671 Expression of spoken language	d330 Speaking d3302 Producing complex spoken messages d340 Producing messages in formal sign language d345 writing messages d360 Using communication devices and techniques	d330-349 Communicating – Producing d350-369 Conversation and use of communication devices and techniques
asking and answering questions and providing explanations	b167 Mental functions of language b1670 Reception of language b1671 Expression of spoken language	d138 Acquiring information d310-d329 Communicating - receiving d330 - d349 Communicating - producing d330 Speaking d350 Conversation d355 Discussion	d130-159 Basic Learning d310-329 Communicating - receiving d330-349 Communicating - producing d350-369 Conversation & use of conversation devices and techniques
recognizing a mistake and correcting it	b1644 Insight b1643 Cognitive flexibility b1646 Problem solving	d163 Thinking d175 Solving problems	d163 Thinking d175 Solving Problems
identifying and solving problems	b1646 Problem Solving	d175 Solving problems	d175 Solving Problems
sequencing multi-step activities	b164 Higher-level cognitive functions	d210 Undertaking a single task d220 Undertaking multiple tasks	d210-220 General tasks and demands
using reason and judgment to make work-related decisions The ability to make simple work-related decisions	b1602 Content of thought b164 Higher-level cognitive functions b1644 Insight b1645 Judgement	d177 Making decisions d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands d2400 Handling responsibilities	d177 Making decisions d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands

Appendix Table 3. B3 Criteria: Concentrate, persist, or maintain pace

This area of mental functioning refers to the abilities to focus attention on work activities and stay on task at a sustained rate.			
12.00 Mental Disorders - Adult	ICF Codes		
SSA B3- Criteria Mental RFC– B Criteria	ICF b-codes Body Function	ICF d-codes Activities/Participation	ICF codes used for ComCog annotation
abilities to focus attention on work activities and stay on task at a sustained rate	b130 Energy and drive functions b140 Attention functions	d160 Focusing attention d210 Undertaking a single task d220 Undertaking multiple tasks	d160 Focusing attention d210-220 General Tasks and demands d230 Carrying out daily routine

The ability to maintain attention and concentration for extended periods	b1400 Sustaining attention	d230 Carrying out daily routine d2303 Managing one's own activity level	
initiating and performing a task that you understand and know how to do	b164 Higher level-cognitive functions b1641 Organization and planning	d210 Undertaking a single task d220 Undertaking multiple tasks d230 Carrying out daily routine	d210-220 General tasks and demands d230 Carrying out daily routine
working at an appropriate and consistent pace	b130 Energy and drive functions b1300 Energy level	d210 Undertaking a single task d220 Undertaking multiple tasks d230 Carrying out daily routine d2303 Managing one's own activity level	d210-220 General tasks and demands d230 Carrying out daily routine
completing tasks in a timely manner	b1140 Orientation to time b164 Higher level cognitive functions b1642 Time management	d210 Undertaking a single task d220 Undertaking multiple tasks d230 Carrying out daily routine d2302 Completing the daily routine d2301 Managing daily routine d2303 Managing one's own activity level	d210-220 General tasks and demands d230 Carrying out daily routine
ignoring or avoiding distractions while working	b140 Attention functions	d160 Focusing attention	d160 Focusing attention
changing activities or work settings without being disruptive	b126 Temperament and personality functions b1261 Agreeableness b164 Higher-level cognitive functions b1643 Cognitive flexibility	d177 Making decisions d230 Carrying out a daily routine d2304 Adapting to changes in daily routine d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands	d177 Making decisions d230 Carrying out daily routine d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands
working close to or with others without interrupting or distracting them The ability to work in coordination with or proximity to others without being distracted by them.	b130 Energy and drive functions b1304 Impulse control b140 Attention functions	d160 focusing attention d177 Making decisions d210 Undertaking single tasks d2103 Undertaking a single task in a group d220 Undertaking multiple tasks d2203 Undertaking multiple tasks in a group d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands	d160 Focusing attention d177 Making decisions d210-220 General tasks and demands d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands

<p>sustaining an ordinary routine and regular attendance at work</p> <p>The ability to perform activities within a schedule, maintain regular attendance and be punctual within customary tolerances.</p> <p>The ability to sustain an ordinary routine without special supervision.</p>	<p>b130 Energy and drive functions</p>	<p>d230 Carrying out a daily routine d2301 Managing daily routine d2302 Completing the daily routine d2303 Managing one's own activity level d2304 Adapting to changes in daily routine d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands d2400 Handling responsibilities</p>	<p>d230 Carrying out a daily routine d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands</p>
<p>working a full day without needing more than the allotted number or length of rest periods during the day</p> <p>The ability to complete a normal workday and workweek without interruptions from psychologically based symptoms</p> <p>Perform at a consistent pace without an unreasonable number and length of rest periods.</p>	<p>b130 Energy and drive functions</p>	<p>d230 Carrying out daily routine d2301 Managing daily routine d2302 Completing the daily routine d2303 Managing one's own activity level d2304 Adapting to changes in daily routine d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands</p>	<p>d230 Carrying out daily routine d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands</p>

Appendix Table 4. B4 Criteria: Adapt or manage oneself

This area of mental functioning refers to the abilities to regulate emotions, control behavior, and maintain well-being in a work setting.			
12.00 Mental Disorders - Adult	ICF Codes		
SSA B4- Criteria Mental RFC- D Criteria	ICF b-codes Body Function	ICF d-codes Activities/Participation	ICF codes used for ComCog annotation
responding to demands	<p>b126 Temperament and personality functions b164 Higher-level cognitive functions</p>	<p>d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands d2400 Handling responsibilities d2401 Handling stress d2402 Handling crisis</p>	<p>d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands</p>
adapting to changes	<p>b164 Higher-level cognitive functions</p>	<p>d230 Carrying out daily routine d2304 Adapting to changes in daily routine</p>	<p>d230 Carrying out daily routine</p>

The ability to respond appropriately to changes in the work setting	b1643 Cognitive flexibility	d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands d2401 Handling stress	d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands
managing your psychologically based symptoms	b164 Higher-level cognitive functions b1641 Organization and planning b1644 Insight	d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands d2401 Handling stress <i>*d570 Looking after one's health</i>	d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands
distinguishing between acceptable and unacceptable work performance	b164 Higher-level cognitive functions b1644 Insight b1645 Judgement	d163 Thinking d177 Making decisions	d163 Thinking d177 Making decisions
setting realistic goals The ability to set realistic goals	b164 Higher-level cognitive functions b1641 Organization and planning b1645 Judgement	d163 Thinking	d163 Thinking
making plans for yourself independently of others The ability to make plans independently of others	b164 Higher-level cognitive functions b1641 Organization and planning b1602 Content of thought	d163 Thinking	d163 Thinking
maintaining personal hygiene and attire appropriate to a work setting	b114 Orientation functions b164 higher level cognitive functions b1645 Judgement	d177 Making decisions	d177 Making decisions
being aware of normal hazards and taking appropriate precautions The ability to be aware of normal hazards and take appropriate precautions	b164 higher level cognitive functions b1644 Insight b1645 Judgement	d177 Making decisions d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands d2401 Handling stress d2402 Handling crisis	d177 Making decisions d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands
The ability to travel in unfamiliar places or use public transportation	b114 Orientation functions b1641 Organization and planning	d175 Solving problems d177 Making decisions d220 Undertaking multiple tasks d2101 Undertaking a complex task <i>**d470 Using transportation</i>	d210-220 General tasks and demands d175 Solving problems d177 Making decisions d210-220 General tasks and demands

*Overlaps with Self-Care & Domestic Life domain

**Overlaps with Mobility domain

The C-2 Criteria in SSA Adult Mental Disorders:

The C2 Criteria is defined as minimal capacity to adapt to changes in one’s environment or to demands that are not already part of one’s daily life; and the inability to function outside of one’s home or a more restrictive setting, without substantial psychosocial supports

Appendix Table 5. SSA C2 Criteria for Adult Mental Disorders

12.00 Mental Disorders - Adult	ICF Codes		
SSA C2- Criteria	ICF b-codes Body Function	ICF d-codes Activities/Participation	ICF codes used for ComCog annotation
Minimal capacity to adapt to changes in one’s environment	b164 Higher-level cognitive functions	d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands	d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands
Minimal capacity to adapt to demands that are not already part of one’s daily life.	b164 Higher-level cognitive functions	d230 Carrying out daily routine d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands d2304 Adapting to changes in daily routine	d230 Carrying out daily routine d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands
changes or increased demands have led to exacerbation of symptoms and signs and to deterioration in functioning.	b164 Higher-level cognitive functions	d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands d2401 Handling stress d2402 Handling crisis	d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands
Unable to function outside of one’s home or a more restrictive setting, without substantial psychosocial supports	b164 Higher-level cognitive functions	d210 Undertaking a single task d220 Undertaking multiple tasks d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands d2401 Handling stress d2402 Handling crisis	d210-220 General Tasks and demands d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands

B2 Criteria: Interact with others. This criterion is generally represented by the Interpersonal Interactions & Relationships (IPIR) domain rather than Communication & Cognition. Appendix Table 6 is included for reference purposes for when Communication & Cognition activities are not found in IPIR codes or possibly overlapping with IPIR codes.

Appendix Table 6. SSA B2 Criteria: Interact with others

This area of mental functioning refers to the abilities to relate to and work with supervisors, co-workers, and the public. While this area of mental functioning is more comprehensively covered in the IPIR areas the table is included for understanding areas of B2 criteria gaps that IPIR does not capture (seen as no IPIR code in the table) and can be captured with Communication & Cognition codes.	
12.00 Mental Disorders - Adult	ICF Codes

SSA B2- Criteria Mental RFC - C	ICF b-codes Body Function – Mental Functions	ICF d-codes Activities/Participation	ICF codes used for IPIR annotation
<p>abilities to <i>relate to</i> and <i>work with</i> supervisors, co-workers, and the public</p> <p>The ability to <i>get along</i> with coworkers or peers without distracting them or exhibiting behavioral extremes</p> <p>The ability to <i>interact appropriately</i> with the general public</p>	<p>b122 Global psychosocial functions b126 Temperament and personality functions b1261 Agreeableness</p>	<p>d710 Basic interpersonal interactions d7100 Respect and warmth in relationships d7101 Appreciation in relationships d7102 Tolerance in relationships d7103 Criticism in relationships d7104 Social cues in relationships d7105 Physical contact in relationships d7106 Differentiation of familiar persons d720 Complex interpersonal interactions d7200 Forming relationships d7201 Terminating relationships d7202 Regulating behaviors within interactions d7203 Interacting according to social rules d730 Relating with strangers d740 Formal relationships d7400 Relating with persons in authority d7401 Relating with subordinates d7402 Relating with equals d750 Informal social relationships d7504 Informal relationships with peers</p>	<p>Interactions (d710-d729) d730 Relating with strangers d740 Formal relationships d7400 Relating with persons in authority d750 Informal social relationships</p>
<p><i>cooperating with others</i></p>	<p>b122 Global psychosocial functions b126 Temperament and personality functions b1261 Agreeableness</p>	<p>d710 Basic interpersonal interactions d7100 Respect and warmth in relationships d7102 Tolerance in relationships d7103 Criticism in relationships d720 Complex interpersonal interactions d7200 Forming relationships d7202 Regulating behaviors within interactions d7203 Interacting according to social rules d730 Relating with strangers d740 Formal relationships d750 Informal social relationships</p>	<p>Interactions (d710-d729) d730 Relating with strangers d740 Formal relationships d750 Informal social relationships</p>

<p><i>asking for help when needed</i></p> <p>The ability to ask simple questions or request assistance</p>	<p>b126 Temperament and personality functions b1266 Confidence b164 Higher-level cognitive functions b1644 Insight b167 Mental functions of language</p>	<p>d710 Basic interpersonal interactions d7100 Respect and warmth in relationships d7101 Appreciation in relationships d720 Complex interpersonal interactions d7203 Interacting according to social rules d730 Relating with strangers d740 Formal relationships d750 Informal social relationships</p> <p><i>d138 Acquiring information</i> d330 Speaking d3301 Producing simple spoken messages d3302 Producing complex spoken messages</p>	<p>Interactions (d710-d729) d730 Relating with strangers d740 Formal relationships d750 Informal social relationships</p>
<p>handling conflicts with others</p>	<p>b122 Global psychosocial functions b126 Temperament and personality functions b1266 Confidence b164 Higher-level cognitive functions b1643 Cognitive flexibility</p>	<p>d710 Basic interpersonal interactions d7102 Tolerance in relationships d7103 Criticism in relationships d720 Complex interpersonal interactions d740 Formal relationships d750 Informal social relationships</p> <p><i>d175 Solving problems</i> d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands</p>	<p>Interactions (d710-d729) d740 Formal relationships d750 Informal social relationships</p>
<p>stating own point of view</p>	<p>b126 Temperament and personality functions b1266 Confidence b167 Mental functions of language</p>	<p>d330 Speaking d3302 Producing complex spoken messages</p>	<p>No IPIR code</p>
<p>initiating or sustaining conversation</p>	<p>b122 Global psychosocial functions b167 Mental functions of language</p>	<p><i>(d330-d349) Communicating - producing</i> d350 Conversation d3501 Sustaining a conversation</p>	<p>No IPIR code</p>
<p>understanding and responding to social cues (physical, verbal, emotional)</p>	<p>b122 Global psychosocial functions b167 Mental functions of language</p>	<p>d710 Basic interpersonal interactions d7104 Social cues in relationships d7105 Physical contact in relationships d720 Complex interpersonal interactions d7203 Interacting according to social rules d7204 Maintaining social space</p> <p><i>d315 Communicating with - receiving - nonverbal messages</i></p>	<p>Interactions (d710-d729)</p>

		d335 Producing nonverbal messages d3350 Producing body language	
responding to requests, suggestions, criticism, correction, and challenges The ability to accept instructions and respond appropriately to criticism from supervisors.	b164 Higher-level cognitive functions b1643 Cognitive flexibility b1644 Insight	d710 Basic interpersonal interactions d7103 Criticism in relationships d720 Complex interpersonal interactions d7202 Regulating behaviors within interactions d7203 Interacting according to social rules d740 Formal relationships	Interactions (d710-d729) d740 Formal relationships
keeping social interactions free of excessive irritability, sensitivity, argumentativeness or suspiciousness	b126 Temperament and personality functions b1261 Agreeableness b1263 Psychic stability b152 Emotional functions b1520 Appropriateness of emotion b1521 Regulation of emotion	d720 Complex interpersonal interactions d7202 Regulating behaviors within interactions d7203 Interacting according to social rules	Interactions (d710-d729)
The ability to maintain socially appropriate behavior	b164 Higher-level cognitive functions b1644 Insight	d710 Basic interpersonal interactions d7101 Appreciation in relationships d7102 Tolerance in relationships d7103 Criticism in relationships D7104 Social cues in relationships d7105 Physical contact in relationships d7106 Differentiation of familiar persons d720 Complex interpersonal interactions d7200 Forming relationships d7201 Terminating relationships d7202 Regulating behaviors within interactions d7203 Interacting according to social rules	Interactions (d710-d729)
...adhere to basic standards of neatness and cleanliness	b114 Orientation Functions b164 Higher-level cognitive functions b1645 Judgement	d720 Complex interpersonal interactions d177 Making decisions	Interactions (d710-d729)

APPENDIX 4: SYNTHETIC NOTE ANNOTATED FOR COMMUNICATION & COGNITION

Below is a synthetic occupational therapy evaluation note that has been annotated for Communication & Cognition information according to the provided legend. Note that any information that resembles PII or PHI does not pertain to any real individual.

Legend:

ComCog Mention = yellow highlight
(ICF Code/Code Ranges, SSA Concept)

OCCUPATIONAL THERAPY EVALUATION NOTE

Details:

Visit Type During This Encounter: Inpatient

Date Of Evaluation Visit: 05/01/2020

Diagnosis: Schizophrenia

Additional Referrals to RMD Services: Recreation therapy; Vocational rehab

English As Preferred Language for Healthcare: Yes(d177, d330_d359)

Subjective:

Patient/Others Comments: Corey Finch is a 23-year-old male currently living with his parents. He was pleasant though reserved on approach and agreeable(d177) to participate in interview. Affect was blunted but able to smile at times, though eye contact was poor. He answered questions(d330_d349) with short replies and latency noted in response(d330_d349) to questions. He reported(d330_d349) that his main concerns at this time are his "disturbing thoughts."

Objective:

Observations/Interview Data: Corey was seen for occupational therapy evaluation on 5/9/20, OT Cooking Group on 5/6/20, and an AMPS (Assessment of Motor and Process Skills) on 5/12/20. Occupational performance was analyzed via chart review, interview, standardized assessment of ADL/IADL performance, and direct observation of performance in a group setting.

Evaluation yielded the following:

Occupational Profile Performance in Areas of Occupation Activities of Daily Living (ADL): Casually dressed; adequately groomed(d210_d220). Reported(d330_d349) that he takes care of daily grooming without reminders.

Instrumental Activities of Daily Living (IADL):

Community Mobility: Reported(d330_d349) that he has a driver's license. Gave conflicting information(d330_d349) about whether he has been driving recently. It appears that he currently relies on his family to transport him as needed.

Financial Management: Reported(d330_d349) receiving SSDI which is deposited in his account. Reported(d330-349) that he budgets his money appropriately and manages his own account (d179, d210_d220). Stated(d330_d349) that his parents supplement his financial support as needed.

Health Management: Reported(d330_d349) that his parents assist with setting up and getting him to medical appointments(d230). Stated(d330_d349) that his mother helps set up his medications in a pill box but that he takes them on his own(d210_d220) and may forget a dose (d163, applied memory) approximately once or twice a week. Able to name (d163, d330_d349, applied memory) the names and doses of his antipsychotic medication.

Home Management & Meal Prep: Corey was vague about his responsibilities/participation in household tasks. **Reported**(d330_d349) that he is responsible for some household tasks such as washing dishes, taking out the trash, and caring for family pets. **Stated**(d330_d349) that he does not do his own laundry. He **reported** (d330_d349) that he helps his mother with cooking sometimes and if he wants to make himself food, he will prepare something simple like oatmeal or a sandwich.

Shopping: Corey is not responsible for shopping for household supplies. He **reported**(d330_d349) **shopping** (d210_d220) independently for personal items.

Education: Corey graduated from HS. He attended a 4-year college full-time for two years and part-time for another year, studying marine biology. He was unable to continue after the onset of symptoms. **Reported**(d330_d349) that he **would like to complete his degree.**(d177)

Work: Corey **reported** (d330_d349) that his last job was "a while back" during summers when he worked as a lifeguard at a local community swimming pool.

Leisure: **listening to music**,(d110_d129) following sports, following current events/**watching**(d130_d159) news programs

Social Participation: It does not appear that Corey has social contact with anyone outside of his immediate family. **Reported**(d330_d349) withdrawing from friends after the onset of his symptoms and does not identify any current friends or social activities. **Stated**(d330_d349) that he gets very anxious in social situations, especially around women who might think "I'm weird."

Client Factors: Corey lost his 10-year-old sister and only sibling when he was 8 years old due to a motor vehicle accident. He **reported**(d330_d349) that he was on the swim team in high school and college before he had to drop out. He has been discouraged by his recent weight gain and he is interested in getting back to swimming. Corey was reluctant to discuss the specific nature of his symptoms but **reported** (d330_d349) that his "intrusive thoughts make it hard to function" and he feels "depressed" about his situation. He **reported**(d330_d349) drowsiness from his medications which causes him difficulty "just getting up and going."

Pain: No pain, 0/10, elicited, observed or reported during this visit

Occupational Performance Skills/Patterns: Corey participated in the Assessment of Motor and Processing Skills (AMPS) on 5/12/20. The AMPS is a standardized evaluation of a person's ability to perform personal and domestic activities of daily living (ADL) tasks. More specifically, when a person is evaluated using the AMPS, the occupational therapist observes the person perform at least two relevant and chosen ADL tasks. The assessment results are as follows: Performance Skills Motor Skills: (Skills needed to move self and objects)

Effort: Demonstrated average clumsiness and effort during IADL task performance

Areas of difficulty: manipulating objects.

The ADL motor ability measure was 0.8 standard deviations above the normative mean, indicating that 21.1% of healthy, well people the same age likely have a higher ADL motor ability measure.

Process Skills: (Skills needed to organize and adapt actions to complete task)

Efficiency: Demonstrated mild degree of disorganization and undesirable use of time, space, or objects. The ADL process ability measure was 1.3 standard deviations below the normative mean, indicating that 90.5% of healthy, well people the same age likely have a higher ADL process ability measure.

Safety: Demonstrated minimal risk for personal injury or environmental damage.

Need for assistance: Demonstrated a minimal degree of need for verbal assistance.

Areas of difficulty: applying knowledge, temporal organization, organizing space and objects, and adapting performance.

Community needs: daily supervision is recommended in the community.

Communication/Interaction Skills: Corey is pleasant and able to make his needs known(d330_d349). However, during the interview and in group setting, Corey appeared preoccupied and had some difficulty attending(d160) to interactions. Responded when directly addressed(d330_d349, d310_d329) but no spontaneous interactions and there was latency in his responses. Asked for questions to be repeated frequently(d330_d349). However, is well-spoken and able to answer questions appropriately(d310_d329, d330_d349) though responses were brief and vague. Able to smile in response to humor(d310_d329).

Habits/Routines/Roles: Corey reported(d330_d349) that at home he generally gets up in the late morning (11 AM-12PM) and spends a great deal of time on his computer or engaged in other solitary or passive activities(d230). He used to swim at his local pool 3-4 times a week but stated, "I haven't done that in a while." He appears to have an established ADL/grooming routine though sometimes needs reminders (d230, applied memory). Reported(d330-349) that he feels he has let his parents down but acknowledges(d330_d349) his parents are supportive.

Affected Areas of Occupation: Activities of daily living; Instrumental activities of daily living; Leisure; Education; Vocation; Social participation

Assessment:

Corey's occupational profile is characterized by modified independence in ADL performance with some difficulty managing IADL, Leisure, Vocation/Education, and Social roles due to experience of symptoms. Though he has been able to live independently in a college setting in the past, he currently relies on the support of his parents. His health condition has limited his present repertoire of occupations and interfered with his ability to achieve age-appropriate roles such as finishing college, working and establishing independent living. His social and community participation is currently very limited. Corey is in the beginning stages of understanding(d310_d329) his health condition. He appears motivated to learn more about his health condition and explore options for managing his symptoms. Corey would benefit from occupational therapy services while on the unit to improve engagement in occupations to support participation in desired roles and life situations in home and community.

Strengths: Corey's strengths include willingness to participate(d177) in therapy, his past educational and social experiences, his past experience in a variety of leisure activities, and generally cooperative attitude. He identified(d330_d349) the following personal strengths: "swimming" and "sciences."

Needs: Corey's needs include further development of coping skills(d240) to support engagement in college and work and increasing social/community participation, establishing a health daily routine(d230), and increasing independence in IADLs. Corey identified(d330_349) the following needs: "social skills" and "improve fitness."

Priorities:(d330_349, d163) "get better, lose weight, and finish degree"

NIHFA OT Score (6-24): 23

Need For Other RMD Services: The Patient has been referred to Vocational therapy and Recreational therapy services.

Plan:

Evaluation & Interventions to Be Coordinated With Interdisciplinary Team:

Interventions: Occupational Therapy to be initiated at this time with individual services as specific needs are identified and unit-based programming per tolerance/availability throughout admission. His progress will be reported in treatment planning meeting on a weekly basis.

Goals:

STGs (within 2 weeks): Corey will:

1. attend next OT Cooking Group session and participate in at least 2 meal preparation tasks with set-up and minimal prompting in order to engage in an essential daily living activity in preparation for returning to supported living in the community.

2. identify at least 3 topics of interest related to self-management in context of OT self-management group in order to promote active engagement in health management.

LTGs (by discharge): Corey will:

1. identify at least 2 specific coping skills he has learned to manage symptoms in order to promote active engagement in health management in preparation for returning to supported living in the community.

2. participate in at least 3 meal preparation tasks in OT Cooking Group with general supervision in order to engage in an essential daily living task in preparation for returning to supported living in the community.

3. identify 2 concrete steps he can take to increase social participation in order to strengthen support network upon returning to supported living in the community.

4. participate in Independent Medication Program for 4 days using environmental modifications in order to strengthen self-management skills in preparation for returning to supported living in the community.

Patient/Caregiver/Significant Other Actively Participated in Goal Setting: Yes

Response To Care: Patient **aware of**(d163) and **agrees to general intervention plan**(d177)

Education:

Services Provided:

Verbal Education: Received verbal education on role of OT services and objectives of OT group sessions.

Learning Demonstrated As Follows: Patient **verbalizes**(d330_349) **understanding**(d310_329); May benefit from review.

Electronic Signatures:

Mathis, Diedre (OTR/L) (Signed 05/12/2020 15:47)

Authored: Evaluation Note, Subjective, Objective, Assessment, Plan, Education

Last Updated: 05/12/2020 15:47 by Mathis, Deidre (OTR/L)

APPENDIX 5: COMMON ABBREVIATIONS FOUND IN CLINICAL DOCUMENTATION OF FUNCTIONING ACTIVITY

act = activity
a.d. = Assist device/ Assistive device
AD = Assistive device
AFO = Ankle foot orthosis
B = bilateral or bilaterally
b/i = bilateral
b/l = bilateral
bp = blood pressure
C/C = Chief or current complaint
CGA = Contact guard assist
CG = Contact guard
dec = decline or declining
d/t = due to
EOB = edge of bed
FO = Foot orthosis
FWW = Front wheeled walker
HEP = Home Exercise Program
HR = heart rate
I = Independent
Ind = Independent
KAFO = Knee ankle foot orthosis
LBQC = Large based quad cane
LTG = long-term goal
NWB = non-weight bearing
Lofstrand crutches = forearm crutches
LB = lower body
LRAD = Less restrictive assistive device
MI = Modified independent
Max assist = Maximum assist/Maximal assist
Min A = Minimum assist/Minimal assist
Mod A = Moderate assist
Mod I = Modified Independence
NWB = non-weight bearing
obs = observed
OOB = out of bed
OT = occupational therapist or occupational therapy
Pt = patient
PA = physical assist
PT = physical therapist or physical therapy
PFRW = platform rolling walker

QC = quad cane
R/W = Rolling walker/ Rollator walker
Rw = rolling walker
STG = short-term goal
S = Supervised/ Supervision
SBA = Stand by assist
SP cane = Single point cane
SPC = Single point cane
SBQC = Small based quad cane
Sup = Supervised/ Supervision
Supv = Supervised/ Supervision
SPV = Supervision
Ther ex = therapeutic exercise
TLSO = thoracolumbosacral orthosis
UB = upper body
VCs = Verbal cues/ Verbal command
v/s = vital signs
w/ = with
w/o = without
W/C = Wheelchair
WHO = wrist/hand orthosis

Tests of Cognitive Function:

GCS =Glasgow Coma Scale
RLAH Levels = Rancho Los Amigos Hospital Levels of Cognitive Functioning Scale
MoCA = Montreal Cognitive Assessment
MMSE = Mini Mental State Examination
Bender-Gestalt II = Bender Visual Motor Gestalt Test/Second Edition
RBANS Update = Repeatable Battery for the Assessment of Neuropsychological Status Update
WAIS-5 = Wechsler Adult Intelligence Scale, Fifth Edition
CDT = Clock Drawing Test
Mini-Cog= Quick Screening for Early Dementia Detection
PPVT-4=Peabody Picture Vocabulary Test-4
Vineland Adaptive Behavior Scales-II
BDI-II Beck Depression Inventory
BVMT-R=Brief Visuospatial Memory Test - Revised (BVMT-R) - Form 2
COWAT=Controlled Oral Word Association Test, FAS/Animals (COWAT)
HVLt-R=Hopkins Verbal Learning Test - Revised (HVLt-R) - Form 2
NAB=Neuropsychological Assessment Battery (NAB) - Language Module - selected subtests - Form 2
WAIS-IV=Wechsler Adult Intelligence Scale, 4th Edition (WAIS-IV) - selected subtests
WMS-IV=Wechsler Memory Scale, 4th Edition (WMS-IV) - selected subtests